

Master's Thesis

Machine Learning for
Computational Creativity:
VST Synthesizer Programming

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Abstract

Learning to create music with an audio production Virtual Studio Technology (VST) synthesizer through sound design and note composition is a time-consuming process, usually obtained through inefficient trial and error and only mastered after years of experience. In this thesis, two educational and creative tools are presented that leverage machine learning to help users program Xfer Records Serum: currently one of the most popular and complex VST synthesizers used by the audio production community. First, a system that provides step-by-step instructions for applying audio effects to change some input audio towards a desired sound is designed. It is demonstrated that the system learns to prioritize effects and can discover more efficient effect order sequences than a variety of baselines. After this, an expressive and controllable variational autoencoder for generating MIDI notes that can then be rendered by a synthesizer is built and some of its creative and artistic applications are explored.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

1.1 Research Background: Audio

1.1.1 Audio Fundamentals

Audio, also known as sound, is created when a pressure wave is transmitted through water, air, or some other medium and consists of a frequency that is perceivable by the human ear. Our ears have evolved to be able to hear a minimum frequency of approximately 20 Hz up to a maximum frequency of approximately 20,000 Hz and this interval is commonly defined as the human hearing range. Sound can be described using three important properties:

1. **Pitch:** the most prominent frequency a sound is perceived to be at; i.e. the position of the sound in the human hearing range.
2. **Intensity:** the volume of the sound, also known as how loud it is. The human ear responds to sound intensity logarithmically, meaning that a sound needs to be approximately ten times more intense to be subjectively perceived as twice as loud.
3. **Timbre:** the "color" of a sound, i.e. everything else about a sound besides pitch and intensity that makes it distinct. For example, a piano, violin, and trumpet could all play a sound with the same pitch and intensity, but each instrument would still sound completely unique due to its specific timbre. **Envelope:** how a sound changes over time, is another important property and plays a big role in defining a sound's timbre.

When combined with human creativity, audio can become music which is found universally in all cultures and locations on Earth. Our ingenuity as a species has allowed us to create and control sound through our voices, musical instruments, and now computer technology with ever increasing precision and thus continuously enabling new auditory possibilities.

1.1.2 Audio Production and Sound Design

Audio production can be broadly defined as the process of creating and manipulating audio in order to craft some desired output audio. When the goal is to create a piece of music, this process typically involves some combination of songwriting, composition, arrangement, audio recording, sound design, editing, mixing, and mastering. This process can also be called music production, specifically electronic music production when the majority of the components of the resulting music are made using a computer.

Electronic music production typically consists of at least one producer using a digital audio workstation (DAW), shown in Figure 1.1, to combine different audio tracks together (for example vocals, drums, bass, lead, pad, etc.) to create a single audio output (usually a

song). Each audio track generally consists of audio samples selected from a sample library, recordings of live audio, and / or sequences of MIDI notes being rendered in real time using a Virtual Studio Technology (VST) synthesizer instrument. Audio effects are applied frequently to audio tracks to change how they sound.

Figure 1.1: User interface of Ableton², a popular digital audio workstation for electronic music production.

Due to computers becoming more powerful, analog audio production tools becoming virtualized, and audio production software and VST plugins becoming cheaper, today anyone with a laptop can create studio quality music and release it to the world via the internet. However, the learning curve for audio production is steep and beginner producers often express frustration with not being able to translate ideas in their head into the DAW. Educational tools are limited and beginners are usually forced to learn via trial and error or from online resources created by others who typically also learned in a similar way. This is why sound design for the music industry is a very difficult task typically done by professionals with years of experience.

²<https://www.ableton.com/en/>

1.1.3 Virtual Studio Technology and Virtualization

Virtual Studio Technology is a software interface that allows audio plugins to be integrated into digital audio workstations. It is an agreed upon software standard that allows makers of audio plugins to rest assured that their plugins will be compatible with different DAWs and computer platforms like Microsoft Windows and Apple OSX. Some examples of VST audio plugin user interfaces are shown in Figure 1.2.

Figure 1.2: User interfaces of several different VST audio plugins.³

Before virtual audio plugins were invented, audio hardware would have to be used and then recorded such that the resulting audio could be converted to a digital format and imported back into a computer to allow for further editing. This made the barrier of entry for music production much higher since an audio producer would need physical access to very expensive audio hardware if they wanted to make use of specific audio effects.

In general, audio hardware has several benefits, for example providing tactile feedback to a user and often creating a more natural sound due to physical imperfections from analogue components. However, it also suffers from several disadvantages like being limited to what is physically possible to build using electronic components, being prone to damage and degradation, taking up physical space, and being expensive. Virtualization allows audio hardware to be simulated by a computer and output digital audio directly into a DAW to then be further manipulated and edited. It is also not limited by the laws of physics, allowing new and creative techniques for making sound to be invented.

The invention of the VST interface allowed anyone with programming skills to create their own audio plugins that are pure software products and therefore take up no space, never physically break, and often cost less than a corresponding physical implementation. Perhaps most importantly, virtualization allows audio plugins to be controlled by a computer and render audio much faster than in real life, thus enabling them to be paired with software algorithms and machine learning.

³<https://www.producerfeed.com/2019/12/the-31-best-free-vst-plugins-of-the-2010s.html>

1.1.4 Synthesizers

Synthesizers are electronic musical instruments that generate audio and are used extensively by audio producers and artists in the music industry. Synthesizers make use of a variety of different techniques to sculpt a sound such as additive synthesis, subtractive synthesis, frequency modulation synthesis, and wavetable synthesis. They typically use one or more oscillators to create an initial audio signal and then manipulate the signal further using various audio effects. Time varying changes to the audio signal, known as modulation, can also be added using low frequency oscillators that are also included in the synthesizer. The envelope of the resulting sound can usually also be adjusted by the user.

Synthesizers are typically played like a piano and consist of knobs and switches to allow the user to control the many different parameters of the synthesizer individually. An example of a synthesizer can be seen in Figure 1.3.

Figure 1.3: Example of a Moog Matriarch Dark synthesizer.⁴

With the relatively recent improvements in computer processing capabilities and the rise of audio plugin virtualization using the VST interface, synthesizers can be written entirely with software and sold as licenses. These are called VST synthesizers and have become increasingly popular with audio producers due to their convenience, affordability, and the various other benefits outlined in Section 1.1.3. For example, Figure 1.4 shows a fully featured, commonly used VST synthesizer that can be played directly in the DAW on a user's computer.

⁴<https://www.musik-produktiv.com/gb/moog-matriarch-dark.html>

Figure 1.4: Graphical user interface of the Sylenth1 VST synthesizer.⁵

1.1.5 Xfer Records Serum

Serum, shown in Figure 1.5 is an advanced wavetable VST synthesizer made by Xfer Records [1]. It consists of:

- Two primary wavetable oscillators
- One noise oscillator
- One sub-bass oscillator
- One highly customizable filter
- Three note envelopes
- Four low frequency oscillators
- 10 built-in audio effects
- The ability to modulate almost every parameter

Serum is currently one of the most popular VST synthesizers in the audio production community and is routinely used by hobbyists and professionals alike. It is a relevant, widely adopted, fully-featured synthesizer that is challenging for humans to master and can be used to craft almost any kind of sound imaginable. It is also reasonably affordable, costing \$189.00 USD and being available via a rent-to-own payment plan on the popular audio production website Splice⁶.

⁵<https://www.lennardigital.com/sylenth1/>

⁶<https://splice.com/>

Figure 1.5: User interface of the Xfer Records Serum VST synthesizer.

1.1.6 Audio Effects

Audio effects are hardware or software devices that manipulate an audio signal. Unlike a synthesizer that can create sound from scratch, an audio effect takes some input audio, changes it in some way, and then emits the modified signal as an output. Overall, audio effects can be thought of as black boxes that transform an audio signal. Figure 1.6 shows a guitarist using a common example of hardware audio effects: guitar pedals such as distortion, overdrive, etc. There are also countless different VST audio effect plugins and many VST synthesizers like Serum come with several common audio effects included.

Figure 1.6: A guitarist using an ensemble of different guitar audio effect pedals.⁷

Compressor

A compressor is an audio effect that compresses a sound's dynamic range. In simpler terms, this means it makes the quieter parts of a signal louder and the louder parts of a signal quieter. Consequently, the resulting audio often sounds "fatter" and this makes compression a very popular audio effect in electronic music production where usually a loud track is a desirable outcome.

Multi-band compression takes this effect a step further and first splits the input signal into multiple bands (often three: lows, mids, and highs) and then applies compression to each band individually before recombining the bands back together, thus allowing different parts of the audio to be compressed by different amounts. For example, a multi-band compressor can be used to compress and bring out the vocals in an audio track since they mostly lie in the mid-band of the audio spectrum. Figure 1.7 displays the controls of the default multi-band compressor in the Ableton DAW.

Figure 1.7: Ableton's multi-band compressor audio effect.

One of Serum's 10 included audio effects is a multi-band compressor and is shown in Figure 1.8. It consists of nine parameters:

1. Threshold
2. Ratio
3. Attack
4. Release
5. Gain
6. Low-band compression amount
7. Mid-band compression amount
8. High-band compression amount
9. Dry / wet amount (mix)

Figure 1.8: Serum's multi-band compressor audio effect.

⁷<https://www.thomann.de/blog/en/the-essential-guitar-pedals-a-beginners-guide/>

Distortion

Distortion is an audio effect used primarily to give a sound a "fuzzier" and "grittier" tone and is especially popular with electric guitarists. It achieves this effect by increasing the gain of an audio signal such that it begins to clip, meaning that the peaks and troughs of the audio signal are being sheared off. This consequently introduces harmonic and inharmonic overtones into the signal, thus resulting in a "warmer", "dirtier" and more "full" sound.

Besides using a dedicated audio effect for distortion, it can also occur naturally in audio hardware such as rackmounts, pre-amplifiers, power amplifiers, and speakers due to the physical processes used to amplify an audio signal. As a result, virtualized distortion effect plugins often include a variety of different distortion algorithms to choose from that try to emulate these different types of distortion found in the real world. Figure 1.9 displays the controls of the default distortion effect in the Ableton DAW.

Figure 1.9: Ableton's distortion audio effect.

One of Serum's 10 included audio effects is distortion and is shown in Figure 1.10. It consists of six parameters:

1. Type of distortion
2. Filter routing (off, filter applied before distortion, or filter applied after distortion)
3. Filter resonance and cutoff frequency
4. Filter type (highpass, bandpass, or lowpass)
5. Drive
6. Dry / wet amount (mix)

Figure 1.10: Serum's distortion audio effect.

Equalizer

An equalizer enables the volume of different parts of the frequency spectrum of an audio signal to be adjusted. It is typically represented as a series of bars or a line across the frequency spectrum (as can be seen in Figure 1.11) indicating which parts are being boosted in volume and which parts are being cut in volume. Equalizers allow the timbre of a sound to be changed significantly by enabling an audio producer to bring out specific frequencies in a sound that are important for vocals, a specific instrument, or some other desired sound profile. They are used extensively in recording studios and most audio playback devices have a simple equalizer built in to allow the listener to adjust the playback to match a specific musical genre (for example, songs with a lot of vocals might have the mid-frequencies boosted for clarity using an equalizer).

Figure 1.11: Ableton's equalizer audio effect.

One of Serum's 10 included audio effects is an equalizer and is shown in Figure 1.12. It consists of eight parameters:

1. Low frequency cutoff
2. Low frequency resonance
3. Low frequency gain
4. Low frequency type (shelf, peak, or high pass filter)
5. High frequency cutoff
6. High frequency resonance
7. High frequency gain
8. High frequency type (shelf, peak, or low pass filter)

Figure 1.12: Serum's equalizer audio effect.

Phaser

A phaser is an audio effect that applies a sweeping, "metallic", or "synthesized" effect to sounds. For example, a human voice can be converted to a robotic sounding voice by applying a phaser to it. The effect is achieved by filtering an audio signal such that a series of peaks and notches are introduced into the frequency spectrum of the signal. These peaks and notches are then often modulated by a low frequency oscillator (LFO) to create the signature sweeping effect of a phaser. For example, Figure 1.13 shows the user interface of a virtualized phaser effect configured such that it applies 16 peaks and troughs centered around 418 Hz to an audio signal.

Figure 1.13: Ableton's phaser audio effect.

One of Serum's 10 included audio effects is a phaser and is shown in Figure 1.14. It consists of six parameters:

1. Rate (in Hz or beats per minute (BPM))
2. Depth
3. Frequency
4. Feedback
5. Phase
6. Dry / wet amount (mix)

Figure 1.14: Serum's phaser audio effect.

Reverb

Reverberation, also known as reverb, is a complex psychoacoustic phenomena defined as the persistence of sound after a sound has been produced. It occurs when the sound waves of some audio reflect off the environment and produce increasingly complicated echos until eventually decaying away and being absorbed by the surrounding material. Reverb provides

a listener with implicit information about the environment something was recorded in. For example, most people can easily distinguish the difference between somebody clapping inside of an empty cavern versus that same person clapping inside of a bedroom full of sound dampening material like blankets and furniture.

Using reverb as an audio effect is incredibly important for electronic music production because it allows artists to simulate virtual instruments to sound as if they had been recorded in a natural environment. By using a reverb audio effect plugin like the one shown in Figure 1.15, audio producers can also recreate the environment an instrument was recorded in, thus making collaborations with other musicians easier. Many different reverberation algorithms exist to simulate the sound of different physical environments and these algorithms are often named correspondingly. For example, hall reverb is a type of reverb that attempts to emulate the impulse response a large room or hall would have.

Figure 1.15: Ableton's reverb audio effect.

One of Serum's 10 included audio effects is reverb and is shown in Figure 1.16. It consists of eight parameters:

1. Type of reverb (hall or plate)
2. Decay
3. High-pass filter cutoff frequency
4. Low-pass filter cutoff frequency
5. Spin amount
6. Spin depth
7. Dry / wet amount (mix)

Figure 1.16: Serum's reverb audio effect.

1.1.7 MIDI

MIDI, also known as Musical Instrument Digital Interface, is a technical standard for allowing musical instruments and software to communicate with one another. For example, by using the MIDI protocol, a physical keyboard can be connected to a computer and used to play the keys on a VST synthesizer running in a digital audio workstation. Music can also be represented using MIDI notes. General MIDI is an extension of the MIDI protocol that contains information like time signatures, tempo, note pitch, velocity, and timing information, along with which instrument is being played out of 128 different supported instrument types. Figure 1.17 shows a portion of a piano song being represented as MIDI notes. Since MIDI is such a common data format for transcribing music, it is also used as training data by many music generation systems.

Figure 1.17: MIDI notes on a piano roll representing the musical contents of a piano piece.⁹

1.1.8 Music Terminology

There are several music theory related terms that are important to the contents of this thesis. They include the following:

- Monophonic: an instrument that can only play a single note at a time.
- Polyphonic: an instrument that can play many notes at a once.
- Chord: three or more notes played at the same time, usually to create a harmony.
- Velocity: numerical value quantifying the dynamics of a note (loud or quiet).
- Microtiming: tiny deviations in note timing introduced by human imperfections when playing an instrument manually.
- Expressiveness: the combination of note dynamics and microtiming that make a sequence sound like a performance or more human.
- Consonance: two or more notes that sound unpleasant when played at once.
- Dissonance: two or more notes that sound pleasant when played at once.
- Bar: a single unit of time containing a specific number of beats played at a particular tempo. A song typically consists of many bars of music.

⁹<https://magenta.tensorflow.org/performance-rnn>

Figure 1.18 is an example of a short segment of music with monophonic and polyphonic instruments represented as MIDI notes along with a piano playing a chord.

Figure 1.18: Four bars of music [2] consisting of four instrument tracks, monophonic MIDI notes, and polyphonic MIDI notes.

1.2 Research Background: Technical

1.2.1 Audio Spectrograms

An audio spectrogram is a visual representation of the frequency content of an audio signal as it changes over time. It can be thought of as a sequence of bar graphs indicating how much of a certain frequency is present in the signal at each point in time. The spectrum of some audio can be calculated using the fast Fourier transform (FFT) which converts the audio signal in the time domain to the frequency domain. Similarly, the spectrogram of some audio can be calculated by dividing the audio signal (which consists of individual samples) into many very small, equally sized sections called frames. A window can then slide over the frames and calculate the fast Fourier transform for each position. How far the window moves forward between each step is called the hop length or the overlap percentage and a typical value is 75%. This process is called the short-time Fourier transform (STFT) and a visual example of it can be seen in Figure 1.19.

Figure 1.19: Example of the short-time Fourier transform being applied to an audio signal.¹¹

Usually the logarithm of spectrograms is taken because the human ear perceives sound in a similar way. Finally, a Mel spectrogram is a special spectrogram where the frequency scale undergoes a non-linear transformation to the Mel scale. Sounds of equal distance from each other on the Mel scale are also perceived by the human ear to be of equal distance in pitch. This is because the human ear perceives the difference between lower frequencies (e.g. 500 Hz and 1000 Hz) to be much larger than the difference between higher frequencies (e.g. 7500 Hz and 8000 Hz). Overall, audio spectrograms are useful because they provide a visual representation of sound and thus are compatible with machine learning techniques and neural network architectures for the image domain.

¹¹<https://stackoverflow.com/questions/59294748>

1.2.2 Audio Cepstra

A cepstrum is created when the inverse Fourier transform of a logarithmic spectrogram is calculated. They are very useful for highlighting periodic structures in audio signals and can be thought of as representing the smoothed spectral envelope of the signal. Figure 1.20 provides a visual comparison between the spectrum and cepstrum of an audio signal.

Figure 1.20: Comparison between audio, its spectrogram, and its cepstrum.¹²

Mel frequency cepstral coefficients (MFCC) are numbers that represent a Mel frequency cepstrum and concisely describe the overall shape of a spectral envelope. They can be calculated for every frame of a Mel spectrogram and then used as a feature for machine learning algorithms.

¹²https://www.researchgate.net/figure/Stages-in-the-cepstrum-analysis-algorithm_fig3_233778945

1.2.3 Deep Learning and Neural Networks

Deep learning is a subfield of artificial intelligence that uses neural networks to learn patterns using typically large amounts of training data. A neural network, also known as an artificial neural network, is a computing system that consists of artificial neurons that loosely model the neurons and synapses in a biological brain. Neural networks are universal function approximators and can be trained on labeled examples using an algorithm called stochastic gradient descent and backpropagation.

A huge benefit of deep learning (DL) is that neural networks can be trained end-to-end on labeled data, skipping the need for the handcrafted feature extraction that is typically required for traditional machine learning techniques. Figure 1.21 highlights the differences between the traditional machine learning process and the deep learning process.

Figure 1.21: Visualization of the difference between traditional machine learning and deep learning for face recognition.¹⁴

1.2.4 Convolutional Neural Networks

A convolutional neural network (CNN) is a specialized neural network with a strong inductive bias for images and two dimensional input data. It typically consists of hierarchical layers of learnable filters that are convolved over their input to learn increasingly complex features. These features are then eventually flattened and converted into an embedding layer which can then be used as the input to a regular neural network to perform a machine learning task like classification. An example of this entire process is shown in Figure 1.22.

¹⁴<https://www.intel.la/content/www/xl/es/artificial-intelligence/posts/difference-between-ai-machine-learning-deep-learning.html>

Figure 1.22: Example of a convolutional neural network for classifying images.¹⁵

1.2.5 Recurrent Neural Networks

A recurrent neural network (RNN), shown in Figure 1.23, is a specialized type of neural network that is well suited for modeling sequences and temporal data. Recurrent neural networks are regular neural networks that allow previous outputs to be used as inputs while having hidden states. These hidden states mean that the neurons of recurrent neural networks have a form of "memory" that enables them to exhibit temporal dynamic behavior. An long short-term memory (LSTM) RNN is a specialized RNN that uses a more complicated neuron which enables it to better remember long-term dependencies, thus making it a good choice for embedding sequential data of arbitrary length into a single vector.

Figure 1.23: Example of a recurrent neural network that has been unrolled to show its hidden states for three timesteps.¹⁷

¹⁵<https://towardsdatascience.com/a-comprehensive-guide-to-convolutional-neural-networks-the-eli5-way-3bd2b1164a53>

¹⁷https://ja.m.wikipedia.org/wiki/file:Recurrent_neural_network_unfold.svg

1.2.6 Autoencoders

An autoencoder, shown in Figure 1.24, is a machine learning model that compresses some input into a lower-dimensional intermediate representation (a latent space) using an encoder and then attempts to reconstruct the input from this representation using a decoder. Usually, a loss function that measures the reconstruction error is used to train the autoencoder so that it learns to reconstruct the input as correctly as possible and consequently learns useful intermediate representations that capture important variations between training examples. For example, autoencoders are great for denoising images since the intermediate representations they learn typically do not have the capacity to include the noise information in an image.

Figure 1.24: Example of an autoencoder for images.¹⁸

1.2.7 Variational Autoencoders

A variational autoencoder (VAE) is an extension of the autoencoder where the lower-dimensional intermediate representation is considered to be a latent representation z where z is a random variable drawn from a prior distribution $p(z)$. A multivariate Gaussian with diagonal covariance is usually used for $p(z)$. In practice, this prior can be implemented using a multivariate normal distribution parameterized by μ and σ . With this framing, the encoder of the VAE now approximates the posterior distribution $p(z | x)$ and the decoder of the VAE now approximates the likelihood distribution $p(x | z)$. When building a VAE with neural networks, these two distributions are consequently parameterized with parameters λ for the encoder ($q_\lambda(z | x)$) and θ for the decoder ($p_\theta(x | z)$).

During training, a variational autoencoder typically uses a loss function that minimizes the reconstruction loss and includes a KL divergence loss term which encourages $q_\lambda(z | x)$, the distribution produced by the encoder, to be similar to the prior distribution $p(z)$ (the multivariate Gaussian with diagonal covariance). More details can be found in Section 5.4.4. The end result of all this is that variational autoencoders are latent variable models that can generate new outputs by sampling from $p(z)$ to obtain a latent vector z and then feeding z to the decoder which can then produce an output since it is parameterized as $p_\theta(x | z)$. A major advantage of a latent space is that vector arithmetic can be easily applied to it to perform operations that would be difficult in the object space. Two examples of this are

¹⁸<https://emkademymedium.com/1-first-step-to-generative-deep-learning-with-autoencoders-22bd41e56d18>

interpolating between objects in a meaningful way (shown in Figure 1.25) and applying attributes of one object to another while maintaining the underlying structure (shown in Figure 1.26).

Figure 1.25: Example of a VAE for sketches [3] interpolating between two human inputs using its latent space.²⁰

Figure 1.26: Example of a VAE for sketches [3] using vector arithmetic in the latent space to add or subtract certain attributes.²⁰

1.2.8 Computational Creativity and Intelligent Music Production

The Association for Computational Creativity²¹ defines computational creativity as:

...a multidisciplinary endeavour that is located at the intersection of the fields of artificial intelligence, cognitive psychology, philosophy, and the arts.

The goal of computational creativity is to model, simulate or replicate creativity using a computer, to achieve one of several ends:

- to construct a program or computer capable of human-level creativity
- to better understand human creativity and to formulate an algorithmic perspective on creative behavior in humans
- to design programs that can enhance human creativity without necessarily being creative themselves

The field of computational creativity concerns itself with theoretical and practical issues in the study of creativity. Theoretical work on the nature and proper definition of creativity is performed in parallel with practical work on the implementation of systems that exhibit creativity, with one strand of work informing the other.

²⁰<https://magenta.tensorflow.org/music-vaе>

²¹<https://computationalcreativity.net/home/>

The third bullet point from the definition, "programs that can enhance human creativity", is the most relevant to the research conducted in this thesis. Intelligent music production (IMP) can be thought of as a subfield of computational creativity and is defined as "the approach of introducing some level of artificial intelligence into the space of music production" [4]. The tools explored in this thesis are applied to music production and make use of artificial intelligence. Therefore, they are also intelligent music production systems.

1.2.9 RenderMan

RenderMan [5] is a command line VST host written in C++ and accessible via Python bindings. It enables VST plugins to be loaded and controlled programmatically, thus making it easier for machine learning to be applied to them. *RenderMan* has the following functionality:

- Loading VST plugin preset files
- Getting VST plugin parameters
- Setting VST plugin parameters
- Obtaining the rendered audio from VST plugins
- Returning various processed forms of that rendered audio

RenderMan also has the advantage that it does not have to play the audio rendered by the VST plugin it controls in real time, meaning that it can be used to collect audio data from a plugin approximately ten times faster than recording the plugin manually. Figure 1.27 shows an example of the tool being used in some Python code.

```
import renderman as rm

# Important settings. These are good general ones.
sampleRate = 44100
bufferSize = 512
fftSize = 512

# This will host a VST. It will render the features and audio we need.
engine = rm.RenderEngine(sampleRate, bufferSize, fftSize)

# Load the VST into the RenderEngine.
path = "/home/tollie/Development/vsts/dexed/Builds/Linux/build/Dexed.so"
engine.load_plugin(path)

# Create a patch generator. We can initialise it to generate the correct
# patches for a given synth by passing it a RenderEngine which has
# loaded a instance of the synthesiser.
generator = rm.PatchGenerator(engine)

# We can also get a string of information about the
# available parameters.
print engine.get_plugin_parameters_description()
```

Figure 1.27: Example of *RenderMan* [5] being used via its Python bindings.

1.2.10 Relevant Python Packages

The following more specialized Python packages are relevant to the research and development conducted in this thesis:

- **Tensorflow**²²: a platform for building and training neural networks with deep learning.
- **Keras**²³: an application programming interface for Tensorflow that makes it much easier to implement the neural network architectures seen in this thesis.
- **librosa** [6]: a library full of essential tools for audio and music analysis. It is used in this thesis to calculate Mel spectrograms and cepstral coefficients.
- **PrettyMIDI** [7]: a package containing many utility functions and classes for handling MIDI data in Python.
- **note-seq** [8]: a library for Google Magenta’s serializable NoteSequence representation that also includes utility functions for analyzing MIDI files. Of interest to this thesis is the chord inference functionality (i.e. given a MIDI file, infer which chords are being played at each point in time).

²²<https://www.tensorflow.org/>

²³<https://keras.io/>

1.3 Research Motivation

The research in this thesis is motivated by the steep learning curve beginners face when getting started with music production, specifically sound design and note composition for a complicated VST synthesizer like Serum. While the internet is an amazing resource, its signal to noise ratio for high quality resources that are also appropriate for what someone is trying to learn is low. Beginners are often forced to learn via trial and error or from online resources created by others who typically also learned in a similar way, making it difficult to assess the quality of these resources before spending time on them. Sound design and note composition are also very subjective processes where there is no "correct" way that can be taught consistently, only heuristics and guidelines exist. As a result, educational tools that inspire a user and highlight new ways of doing something can be a lot more useful than prescriptive tools attempting to teach a specific set of rules.

An analogy also helps explain the motivation behind this area of research. Music production can be considered to be similar to cooking in that most casual people do not invent completely new recipes from scratch, but rather begin with a desired type of cuisine, then search for and follow a base recipe to achieve their desired outcome and often modify and customize the recipe along the way. Over time they develop the skills to deviate more from recipes or even create dishes entirely from scratch. Audio production is similar in that producers often begin with a desired style of sound, melody, or track idea (potentially subconsciously) based on some combination of other artists, tracks, and personal experiences. This idea is then refined through a mixture of skill, trial and error, creativity, and personal preferences. It is also common practice for audio producers to have reference tracks from other artists directly in their DAW to draw inspiration from during production. However, DAW project files are rarely open sourced and therefore the "recipes" available online in the form of tutorials or blog posts to create a specific sound or composition are inconsistent or simply not available. Finally, the steps or even "ingredients" of a sound can be very non-obvious which is why professional sound design is done by experts with years of experience.

Finally, the research in this thesis is also motivated by the relatively recent explosion in machine learning and the rise of intelligent music production. Due to the democratization of music production through virtualization technology enabling anyone to create music on a laptop, educational tools built for this environment have a rapidly increasing amount of potential users who could benefit from them. For the same reasons, advances in machine learning and computational creativity also have an increasingly important impact on the music production community, especially when they enable new ways for humans and artificial intelligence to create art collaboratively.

With all of this in mind, this thesis explores two educational intelligent music production systems that collectively help a beginner to learn how to create a desired sound using a fully featured VST synthesizer and then explore the endless possibilities of composing notes for the synthesizer. The intention is that building these systems and understanding the processes that power them helps alleviate some of the difficulties mentioned previously and contributes more educational, collaborative, and controllable approaches to the fields of computational creativity and intelligent music production.

1.4 Thesis Outline

This thesis is organized as follows:

Front Matter

Chapter 1: Introduction to the thesis and its motivation along with the prerequisite background information for audio, music production, machine learning, and specific tools used.

Chapter 2: Related works in the areas of intelligent music production, audio modeling, audio effect modeling, audio VST parameter programming, and MIDI note generation.

Chapter 3: Research proposal including related work shortcomings, objectives, approach, and contributions of the thesis.

Chapter 4: Overview, data collection / preprocessing / modeling details, evaluation results, and discussion for System 1: *SerumRNN*.

Chapter 5: Overview, data collection / conditioning / modeling details, evaluation results, artistic applications, and discussion for System 2: *LH3BDVAE*.

Chapter 6: Discussion about *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* as complementary systems along with the relevant limitations, ethical considerations, and future directions of work.

Chapter 7: Conclusion and final remarks.

Appendix A: Additional evaluation results for *SerumRNN*.

Appendix B: Additional evaluation results for *SerumRNN*.

Acknowledgements

List of Acronyms

Bibliography

Chapter 2

Related Works

This thesis builds on a number of related works in the fields of computational creativity, audio signal processing, and machine learning. These related works can be placed into five categories:

- **Intelligent Music Production:** systems built to aid music producers with artificial intelligence.
- **Audio Modeling:** systems that attempt to model raw audio directly.
- **Audio Effect Modeling:** systems that attempt to model audio effects directly.
- **Audio VST Parameter Programming:** systems that attempt to model the parameters of audio VST plugins.
- **MIDI Note Generation:** systems that generate MIDI notes which can then be rendered by an audio VST synthesizer.

Inspiration is taken from all five categories in order to develop the two systems proposed in this thesis. Some shortcomings of the related works that influence the research objectives of this thesis are discussed in Section 3.1

2.1 Intelligent Music Production

As mentioned in Section 1.1.2, music production is the process of creating and manipulating audio in order to craft some desired output music. Moffat and Sandler [4] define intelligent music production (IMP) as "the approach of introducing some level of artificial intelligence into the space of music production". They provide a comprehensive overview of the state (as of summer 2019) of intelligent music production and define a generalized flow diagram, visible in Figure 2.1, that intelligent music production tools generally adhere to. They also stress the importance of considering how an individual will interact with an IMP system and the potential for IMP systems to produce new and interesting approaches for analyzing and manipulating audio.

Some specific prior works of intelligent music production tools are investigated in order to obtain insight into building systems that can collaborate with the user rather than attempting to replace them entirely. Sommer and Ralescu [9] propose a program that learns how a performer modifies the parameters of a synthesizer during live performances and can then perform these adjustments automatically, thus freeing the performer from this responsibility. Chen, Smith, and Yang [10] create a dataset and build a tool using a CNN that estimates the compatibility of two audio loops, enabling artists to search through their audio production libraries consisting of thousands of audio loops much more efficiently.

Figure 2.1: A generalized flow diagram of an intelligent music production tool [4].

Lastly, *Neural Loops* by Thio and Donahue [11] is a co-creation tool that allows users to explore and manipulate musical loops synthesized by neural network generative models. It is an intelligent musical sequencer where users can independently change the resulting audio making it music creation software that does not assume expertise, but still allows customization.

Finally, commercially available intelligent music production products are also surveyed to obtain knowledge about potential applications and robust implementations. Perhaps the most successful example is *Spleeter* [12] by Deezer: a fast and state-of-the-art music source separation tool with pre-trained models. *Spleeter* has essentially become the industry standard for separating vocals and other instruments into individual tracks, enabling artists to remix and edit songs much more easily. It is one of the best examples of intelligent music production tools becoming adopted by the mainstream, non-research oriented music production community. Similarly, *Landr*¹ provides automatic music mastering using artificial intelligence, making an expensive and tedious process much more accessible to non-professionals. *Sononym*² uses audio analysis, clustering, and other machine learning algorithms to organize music production sample libraries. This allows its users to search and browse for audio samples using several new dimensions such as audio similarity to other samples and automatically organizes large sample libraries, therefore increasing the time an artist can spend on creative efforts. Lastly, *Magenta Studio* [13], shown in Figure 2.2, is an excellent example of some of the most recent deep learning approaches for MIDI note generation and manipulation being packaged in a simple and intuitive user interface, thus making these models accessible to all.

¹<https://www.landr.com/>

²<https://www.sononym.net/>

Figure 2.2: User interfaces of *Magenta Studio* [13].

2.2 Audio Modeling

Neural network architectures that output raw audio are required to model audio in some form. While this thesis does not involve building systems with the objective to output raw audio, understanding the model architectures, feature extraction techniques, audio preprocessing steps, and loss functions of the prior works in this category is highly beneficial for the design of System 1 of this thesis.

Autoregressive waveform models generate an audio signal one sample at a time. Some significant examples of this are Oord et al.’s *WaveNet* [15], Mehri et al.’s *SampleRNN* [15], Kalchbrenner et al.’s *WaveRNN* [16], Verma and Chafe’s raw audio transformer model [17], and Dhariwal et al.’s *Jukebox* [18]. While creating audio at the sample level allows any audio to be generated with a high degree of freedom, these models typically require very large and data-hungry neural networks along with expensive computational resources due to the high information density of raw audio data. They also cannot take advantage of spectral based loss functions that can measure perceived audio similarity better than using raw waveforms (since different waveform shapes can sound identical to the human ear).

There also exist less computationally complex methods of modeling audio like generating waveforms directly with overlapping frames using strided convolutions. Some examples of this are Défossez et al.’s *SING* [19], Arik, Jun, and Diamos’s *MCNN* [20], and Donahue, McAuley, and Puckette’s *WaveGAN* [21]. Audio can also be modeled using spectrograms and then converting them back to the time domain as is the case for Wang et al.’s *Tacotron* [22] and Engel et al.’s *GANSynth* [23]. These approaches also suffer from their own unique difficulties like the phase-alignment problem and spectral leakage, but can take advantage of spectral audio similarity loss functions that can better represent perceived audio similarity.

Lastly, Engel et al.’s *NSynth* [24] and *DDSP* [25] are autoencoder models that learn a latent representation of the audio data they are trained on. *NSynth* uses the *WaveNet* architecture for its encoder and decoder and therefore generates audio at the individual sample level. Through its latent space, it provides artists with intuitive control over the timbre and dynamics of the generated sound and gives them the ability to explore new sounds that are difficult or impossible to produce with a hand-tuned synthesizer. The *DDSP* model, shown in Figure 2.3 uses a strong inductive bias in order to model audio very efficiently by passing parameters through differentiable implementations of known sound synthesis algorithms. It operates at the spectral level and uses a multi-scale spectrogram loss that enables it to compare the similarity of two samples of audio at different spatial-temporal resolutions. *DDSP*’s latent representation and autoencoder architecture enables it to be used for timbre transfer: rendering some input audio (e.g. the human voice) as a different instrument (e.g. violin, trumpet, etc.).

Figure 2.3: Architecture of the *DDSP* [25] model.

2.3 Audio Effect Modeling

There has also been a reasonable amount of research on modeling audio effects directly using artificial intelligence. These related works attempt to learn the changes some black box audio effect makes to an input signal by processing the audio directly and outputting the corresponding "wet" audio, often enabling them to be trained end-to-end. While this direct approach is usually not compatible with programming the parameters of existing VST audio plugins, these related works also contain interesting neural network architectures, audio processing approaches, and loss functions applicable to the research in this thesis.

Ramírez and Reiss [26] show that one-dimensional convolutional neural networks can learn to process audio directly such that it matches the target audio produced by an equalizer audio effect for shelving, peaking, lowpass, and highpass equalization tasks. Ramírez, Benetos, and Reiss are then able to extend this work to end-to-end modeling of a plate and spring reverb audio effect [27] and finally they build a general purpose neural network [28, 29] for modeling a variety of other non-linear black box audio effects. Nercessian, Sarroff, and Werner [30] are able to adequately model a BOSS MT-2 pedal distortion audio effect using a lightweight 210-parameter neural network by taking advantage of differentiable cascaded biquads and Damskågg et al. [31] and Wright et al. [32] are successfully able to emulate guitar amplifier audio effects via a traditional black-box neural network approach. Steinmetz and Reiss [33] demonstrate that temporal convolutional neural networks can be used to achieve state-of-the-art performance for modeling a complex dynamic range compressor audio effect while using 100 times less training data than previous methods and being able to perform real time inference using a CPU.

Finally, contrasting all the previous deep learning approaches for modeling audio effects directly, Ly and Villegas' *Genetic Reverb* [34] is able to learn a parameterized room impulse response and apply it to some input audio (thus making it a reverb audio effect) by using a genetic algorithm. The authors then implement *Genetic Reverb* as a Matlab audio plugin.

2.4 Audio VST Parameter Programming

Audio VST parameter programming is the act of using artificial intelligence to predict and program the parameters of a black box audio effect or synthesizer, which is then used to render the resulting output audio. While this is a relatively niche research area, there are several foundational related works that System 1 of this thesis builds upon.

To begin, some research has been conducted to program synthesizer parameters without neural networks or deep learning. Heise, Hlatky, and Loviscach [35] learn to clone a target sound with a synthesizer by programming its parameters using a particle swarm optimization algorithm and a Mel frequency cepstral coefficient (MFCC) based audio similarity measure. Cáceres [36] make use of K-means clustering, tree search, and gradient descent to learn the parameter values for target sounds generated using frequency modulation (FM) synthesis. Macret and Pasquier [37] tackle this problem using a novel approach of representing the synthesizer parameters as a programming language and applying mixed-type cartesian genetic programming to learn them. Two years later, Tatar, Macret, and Pasquier [38] build on this work to create *PresetGen*, a system that can program the parameters of a real life synthesizer (the OP-1 by Teenage Engineering) using a multi-objective non-dominated sorting genetic algorithm. Lastly, Smith [39] builds a generic system for reverse engineering the parameters of VST synthesizers and audio effects by also leveraging a genetic algorithm.

Neural-based methods of programming a VST synthesizer are the most relevant to the research in this thesis. Yee-King, Fedden, and d’Inverno [40] learn to program the Dexed VST synthesizer using a deep bidirectional LSTM recurrent neural network and at the same time also develop *RenderMan* [5] (see Section 1.2.9) in order to facilitate collecting training data for their system. They also compare their neural approach to a genetic algorithm baseline. Figure 2.4 displays a diagram of their approach which is similar to the process explored in this thesis.

Figure 2.4: Diagram of Yee-King, Fedden, and d’Inverno’s [40] process for programming the parameters of the Dexed VST synthesizer.

InverSynth [41] by Barkan et al. is probably the most similar to System 1 of this thesis because it uses a deep convolutional neural network to program the parameters of a VST synthesizer from the spectrograms of some input and target audio. The authors use a variety of different spectral audio similarity metrics to evaluate the model and also compare the system against a version that learns the synthesizer parameters directly from the raw audio. They find that the network depth of *InverSynth* is an important factor that contributes to the prediction accuracy. *InverSynth*’s architecture is shown in Figure 2.5.

Figure 2.5: Architecture of *InverSynth* [41], a VST synthesizer parameter programming system.

Finally, Esling et al. [42] use a variational autoencoder consisting of a CNN encoder and decoder and normalizing flows to learn a latent space that represents the parameters of the Diva VST synthesizer. They also make use of *RenderMan* [5] to control the synthesizer programmatically and collect training data. A diagram of their approach is displayed in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6: Diagram of Esling et al.’s [42] process for programming the parameters of the Diva VST synthesizer.

All of the previous neural-based VST synthesizer parameter programming systems approach the problem with a one-shot, black-box process and focus more on synthesis rather than applying effects. The author believes this end-to-end approach replaces a user more than it augments them and results in fewer opportunities to learn. In addition to this, many users typically know how to begin programming their desired sound via oscillator, attack, decay, sustain, and release parameters, but have difficulty programming the relevant effects due to the sheer number of combinatorial possibilities.

Neural-based methods for programming VST audio effect plugin parameters are also very relevant to this thesis. Mimitakis, Bryan, and Smaragdis [43] build a system that enables one-shot parametric style transfer by learning the parameters of an equalizer audio effect using a Siamese convolutional neural network architecture operating on input and target audio spectrograms. Sheng and Fazekas [44] also use a Siamese CNN model to learn the parameters of a dynamic range compressor audio effect. Steinmetz et al. [45] build a differentiable mixing console consisting of a collection of neural networks with a strong inductive bias for multitrack audio mixing. They are able to perform end-to-end audio mixing via a collection of audio effects including equalization, compression, reverb, fading, and panning. Lastly, *DeepAFx* [46] by Ramírez et al. enables any VST audio effect to be included into a neural network as a non-differentiable black box layer by calculating its gradient using a stochastic gradient approximation scheme, a delay-invariant loss function, and a stateful distributed training strategy. The authors demonstrate the success of this approach on a variety of different audio production tasks including tube amplifier emulation, non-speech sounds removal, and automatic music mastering. The flow of audio, parameters, and gradients in their system can be seen in Figure 2.7.

Figure 2.7: Diagram of the flow of audio, parameters, and gradients in the *DeepAFx* [46] system.

This thesis also takes inspiration from research unrelated to the audio and music domain. Most notable is *Exposure* [47] by Hu et al. from Microsoft Research. *Exposure* is a white-box photo post-processing framework that applies image effects to a photo to improve it and change it towards some visual style desired by the user. An example sequence of the system re-touching an image and applying various different effects to it is shown in Figure 2.8. While the techniques for training *Exposure* are quite different than the ones used in this thesis, its iterative approach with intermediate steps is very similar to the first system developed in this thesis.

Figure 2.8: Diagram of *Exposure* [47] applying image effects using a step-by-step approach to change some input photo towards some desired style.

2.5 MIDI Note Generation

System 2 of this thesis deals with MIDI note composition and symbolic music generation for which there is a lot of related research. Ji, Luo, and Yang [48] provide a comprehensive survey on the current state (as of Fall 2020) of deep music generation architectures, representations, algorithms, evaluations, and datasets. Their survey also includes systems that render audio directly like the ones mentioned in Section 2.2.

System 2 of this thesis is based in part off the architectures of Roberts et al.’s *MusicVAE* [49] (shown in Figure 2.9) and Simon et al.’s *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] (shown in Figure 2.10). These models consist of bidirectional LSTM recurrent neural network variational autoencoders that are able to learn a latent space that encodes the training dataset of MIDI notes. Just like any other VAE, they can encode existing music into their latent space, sample their latent space to generate music, and perform vector arithmetic within their latent space to interpolate between musical sequences and add / subtract musical attribute vectors. *Multi-track MusicVAE* is an extension of *MusicVAE* and is able to model multiple instruments, polyphonic notes, and note dynamics and can be controlled with a conditioning sequence to output music following a specific chord progression.

Figure 2.9: Architecture of *MusicVAE* [49].

Building on this work, more complicated note composition models exist like *PianoTree VAE* [50] by Wang et al. which focuses on better polyphonic music generation via a novel sparse encoding of music and a novel hierarchical architecture shown in Figure 2.11. Another example that is not a variational autoencoder is *BandNet* [51] by Zhou et al. where music theory knowledge is integrated into a LSTM RNN composition model to learn how to generate music in the style of the Beatles.

There are also quite a few prior works on MIDI note generation without using a recurrent neural network. *MuseGAN* [52] by Dong et al. and *DMB-GAN* [53] by Guan, Yu, and Yang both leverage a generative adversarial network (GAN) to generate multi-track music. *DMB-GAN* employs a self-attention mechanism and a dual generative adversarial architecture with a branch for each track to ensure harmonic structure among all instrument tracks. Besides generative adversarial networks, the relatively recent rise of transformer models has also held true for symbolic music generation. Huang et al.’s *Music Transformer* [54], Huang and Yang’s *Pop Music Transformer* [55], Jiang et al.’s *Transformer VAE* [56], and Wu and Yang’s *MuseMorphose* [57] all utilize transformers in their architectures and can consequently better model long musical sequences and the resulting long-term dependencies. *Transformer VAE* and *MuseMorphose* are both variational autoencoders and are therefore able to take advantage of the properties of latent spaces mentioned earlier.

Figure 2.10: Architecture of *Multi-track Music VAE* [2].

Figure 2.11: Architecture of *Pianotree VAE* [50] for polyphonic note composition.

Research about capturing musical expressiveness and being able to control the output of MIDI note composition models is also very pertinent to System 2 of this thesis. One example of this is *GrooveVAE* [58] by Gillick et al. which captures the expressiveness and groove of human generated drum beats by including note dynamics and microtiming information in its musical note representation. The system can then be used to make static or plain drum beats sound more natural (also known as drum humanization) and create drum patterns in a specific groove. *PerformanceRNN* [59] by Simon and Oore does something similar for piano notes using a LSTM recurrent neural network that can model expressive timing and the dynamics of polyphonic piano notes via a custom note representation.

Herremans and Chew's *Morpheus* [60] and the variational autoencoder built by Guo et al. [61] both incorporate spiral tension array theory into their models to enable the user to control the tonal tension of the generated music. Figure 2.12 illustrates how tension information is calculated between different musical chords. The *Morpheus* system focuses on preserving long-term musical structure and Guo et al. demonstrate that "tension feature vectors" can be identified in the model's latent space and used to control its output.

Figure 2.12: Illustration of three ways to measure tension between a C major and C major chord shown in a pitch class helix of a spiral array: cloud diameter, cloud momentum, and tensile strain [60].

Valenti, Carta, and Bacciu introduce *MusAE* [62]: a music adversarial autoencoder that is able to capture and embed music genre and style information in its latent space. In contrast to all the neural-based music generation methods, Valenti, Carta, and Bacciu propose a statistical machine learning model that is able to capture melody, chord, and bass style from a single pop song and imitate the style with structure information in a new and complete piece. Mittal et al. [63] extend *MusicVAE* with denoising diffusion probabilistic models to enable parallel note generation. Without this improvement, autoregressive models like *MusicVAE* are limited to generating one note at a time. Finally, Zhou et al. [64] present an interactive system that supports generative melody composition with human-in-the-loop Bayesian optimization which helps a user find a desired melody within the model's latent space.

System 2 of this thesis also takes inspiration from Google Magenta's *LoFi Player* [65] built by Thio and Eck. *LoFi Player* is an art project that provides a visual user interface for a specialized implementation of *Multi-track MusicVAE*. It generates continuous relaxing lo-fi hip hop music while providing intuitive control over the music. The user can change the chord progression, tempo, toggle instruments, and more by clicking on various sections of the user interface shown in Figure 2.13.

Figure 2.13: User interface of *LoFi Player* [65].

Chapter 3

Research Proposal

3.1 Related Work Shortcomings

As explored in the previous section, there are several related works for audio VST synthesizer programming and MIDI note composition. However, the audio VST parameter programming systems all suffer from one or more of the following pertinent problems:

- They are applied to toy VST audio plugins with little practical use.
- They are incompatible with existing VST audio plugins.
- They are incompatible with controlling multiple different audio effects.
- Their inference time is prohibitively long.
- They are black-boxes with uninterpretable results.
- They do not break the parameter programming process into smaller steps.
- They aim to replace a user entirely.

Similarly, while the MIDI note generation related works featured in Section 2.5 are more established and developed, they also suffer from one or more of the following points that are relevant to this thesis:

- They lack extensive controllability by the user.
- They do not capture how pleasant music is to the listener (e.g. note harmoniousness).
- They do not capture the expressiveness in music (e.g. note dynamics like velocity and microtimings).
- They are limited to a specific instrument.
- They use complicated architectures that are difficult to adapt to new applications.
- They lack an intuitive user interface to enable them to be applied or interacted with artistically by non-technical users.

This collection of shortcomings shapes the research objectives of the two systems examined in this thesis.

3.2 Research Objective

The objective of this thesis is to build computational creativity tools that utilize machine learning to reduce the steep learning curve beginners face when getting started with music production and VST synthesizer programming. These tools focus on tackling two specific processes required for making music with a VST synthesizer:

1. **Sound Design:** creating a desired timbre of sound by programming the parameters of the synthesizer and applying appropriate audio effects.
2. **Note Composition:** creating music by providing the synthesizer with notes to render after its parameters have been programmed.

The author also believes that when using an AI assisted system, the user's sense of ownership over their work should be preserved. As a result, this is treated as another research objective and an emphasis is placed on building controllable and collaborative tools. Assuming one system is developed for each of the two processes listed above, more granular research objectives can then be defined for each system.

Sound Design System Research Objectives

- Takes as input a desired sound and helps a user program a VST synthesizer to produce sound similar in timbre to the input sound
- Applicable to a fully featured VST synthesizer used by amateurs and professionals alike
- Compatible with multiple different commonly used audio effects that are built into the synthesizer
- Fast inference time (less than three seconds)
- Focuses on user education and produces interpretable intermediate results
- Pushes the user in the right direction without trying to replace them entirely (i.e. the user has a reasonable level of control over the output of the system)

Note Composition System Research Objectives

- Generates multi-instrument tracks of MIDI notes at least four bars in length that can then be fed to a VST synthesizer to render
- Gives a high degree of control to the user to enable the discovery of a wide variety of different note compositions and styles
- Generates both consonant and dissonant music (i.e. captures note harmoniousness information)
- Generates expressive music (i.e. captures note dynamics and microtiming information)
- Extensible: can be applied to several different artistic applications and made accessible to non-technical users

3.3 Research Approach

The research objectives from the previous section are addressed through the design, implementation, and evaluation of two machine learning systems: one for the sound design process and one for the note composition process required for making music with a VST synthesizer.

System 1 is a tool called *SerumRNN* that can perform step-by-step VST synthesizer audio effect programming. It iteratively changes some input audio towards the timbre of some desired target audio by applying audio effects one after the other through programming the parameters of the Serum VST synthesizer, resulting in a sequence of interpretable intermediate steps. Figure 3.1 provides a high-level overview of System 1.

The iterative approach used by *SerumRNN* is inspired by a similar task in the image domain: retouching photographs. A particularly relevant example is *Exposure* [47], a step-by-step white-box automatic image post-processing system shown in Figure 2.8 of Section 2.4. *SerumRNN* also aims to provide a user experience similar to other collaborative production tools [9, 11] that can educate and augment a user rather than aiming to replace them entirely.

Figure 3.1: High-level overview of *SerumRNN*.

Xfer Records Serum is chosen as the VST synthesizer because it is a relevant, widely adopted, fully-featured synthesizer that is challenging for humans to master and loved by the audio production community. Choosing a popular and powerful synthesizer like Serum maximizes the practicality of System 1 since it becomes more applicable to a larger pool of potential users.

SerumRNN is built using an ensemble of neural networks working together to learn what sequence of audio effects to apply to the input audio and how to program the parameters of these effects. Five commonly used audio effects in Serum are supported: multi-band compression, distortion, equalizer, phaser, and reverb, and the system is applied to a large sample of different initial input sounds ranging from simple to very complex. *SerumRNN* is evaluated using several audio similarity metrics and compared against five baselines to determine the advantages of an iterative approach that considers the order of audio effects applied to the input sound.

System 2 is a tool called *LH3BDVAE* that can compose eight bar long note sequences for four instruments at once: lead, harmony, bass, and drums. These note sequences can then be fed to Serum or any other VST synthesizer to be rendered as music, or used for a variety of other artistic purposes.

The system is implemented using a conditional hierarchical variational autoencoder neural network and is trained on a large dataset of MIDI files. Its architecture takes inspiration from Google Magenta’s *MusicVAE* [49] (model architecture displayed in Figure 2.9 of Section 2.5), *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] (model architecture displayed in Figure 2.10 of Section 2.5), and *GrooveVAE* [58]. Due to this, the overall focus for this system is less on novelty in the machine learning domain, and more on controllability and novel artistic applications of it. A high-level overview of *LH3BDVAE* can be found in Figure 3.2.

Figure 3.2: High-level overview of *LH3BDVAE*.

LH3BDVAE is built as a conditional model, making it highly controllable by the user. In total, 18 different dimensions can be tweaked independently when interacting with the system. Two of these dimensions can be used to control how consonant or dissonant the generated notes are and the model is also able to learn musical expressiveness through MIDI note velocity information and note timing imperfection values.

LH3BDVAE is evaluated quantitatively on its note composition ability using several different sampling and reconstruction metrics across all of its outputs. It is also evaluated qualitatively on its extensibility as a creative tool via five different artistic applications, two of which have been accepted to international AI art galleries.

3.4 Contributions

The primary contribution of this thesis is the development and evaluation of two systems that can together tackle specific portions of the sound design and note composition processes required for making music with a VST synthesizer.

The research conducted for System 1 / sound design / VST synthesizer parameter programming results in contributions that focus primarily on machine learning and intelligent music production. Chapter 4 of this thesis demonstrates that *SerumRNN*:

- Is applicable to a fully featured VST synthesizer used extensively by the audio production community.
- Uses a novel approach consisting of an ensemble of neural networks to learn how to program VST synthesizer parameters.
- Significantly reduces the error between the input and target audio.
- Benefits from applying effects iteratively in a specific order.
- Learns which effects are most important.
- Provides interpretable and meaningful intermediate steps.
- Can discover more efficient effect order sequences than a variety of baselines.

As mentioned in the previous section, the research conducted for System 2 / note composition / music generation does not make use of novel machine learning. Instead, its contributions are related to user controllability and the flexibility of the system to be adapted for new artistic applications in the field of computational creativity. Chapter 5 of this thesis demonstrates that *LH3BDVAE*:

- Can compose eight bar note sequences for four instruments at once: lead, harmony, bass, and drums.
- Is highly controllable, giving the user the ability to change 18 different musical attributes independently.
- Combines multi-instrument, polyphonic, expressive, and controllable note generation into one system.
- Can be adapted and extended to several different artistic applications that enable intuitive interaction with thousands of non-technical users.

Chapter 4

System 1: *SerumRNN*

4.1 Overview

System 1 is a tool that can perform step-by-step VST synthesizer audio effect programming. It is called *SerumRNN* and iteratively changes an input audio towards the same timbre of a desired target audio by sequentially applying audio effects via the Serum VST synthesizer. As a result, the system provides a sequence of interpretable intermediate steps. Figure 3.1 from Section 3.3 provides an overview of this approach.

SerumRNN uses a novel approach consisting of an ensemble of models working together: an *effect selection model* to determine which effect to apply next to the input audio and then a collection of *effect parameter models*, one per supported effect, to program the selected effect parameters. An example of *SerumRNN* applying three steps to some input audio can be seen in Figure 4.1. Audio examples can be listened to at https://bit.ly/serum_rnn.

Figure 4.1: Mel spectrogram progression of the system applying three effects to a user's input audio.

4.2 Data Collection

Data collection and processing systems represent a significant portion of the software engineering required for *SerumRNN*. Training data for all models is generated by rendering audio samples from Serum and then converting them into spectrograms and cepstra. Due to the complexity of Serum and its effects, virtually infinite amounts of training data can be generated.

4.2.1 Audio Rendering

Table 4.1: Parameters sampled from the Serum VST synthesizer.

Effect	Parameter Name	Type	Sampled Values
Compressor	Low-band Compression	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Compressor	Mid-band Compression	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Compressor	High-band Compression	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Distortion	Mode	Categorical	12 classes
Distortion	Drive	Continuous	[0.3, 1.0]
Equalizer	High Frequency Cutoff	Continuous	[0.50, 0.95]
Equalizer	High Frequency Resonance	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Equalizer	High Frequency Gain	Continuous	[0.0, 0.4] and [0.6, 1.0]
Phaser	LFO Depth	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Phaser	Frequency	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Phaser	Feedback	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Hall Reverb	Mix	Continuous	[0.3, 0.7]
Hall Reverb	Low Frequency Cutoff	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]
Hall Reverb	High Frequency Cutoff	Continuous	[0.0, 1.0]

Five commonly used and predominantly timbre altering effects are chosen for training data collection: multi-band compression, distortion, equalizer (EQ), phaser, and hall reverb. Table 4.1 summarizes which Serum synthesizer parameters are sampled for each supported effect. Continuous parameters (knobs on the Serum synthesizer) can be represented as floating-point numbers between zero and one inclusively. Categorical parameters can be represented as one-hot vectors of length C where C is the number of classes. Continuous parameter sampling value ranges are occasionally limited to lie within practical, everyday use regions.

Furthermore, in order to apply the system to a variety of different sounds, data is collected from 12 different synthesizer presets split into three groups (in increasing order of complexity): *Basic Shapes*, *Advanced Shapes*, and *Advanced Modulating Shapes*. The *Basic Shapes* preset group consists of single oscillator sine, triangle, saw, and square waves. Next, the *Advanced Shapes* preset group consists of the dry (no effects) dual oscillator "LD Power 5ths", "SY Mtron Saw", "SY Shot Dirt Stab", and "SY Vintage Bells" default Serum presets. Finally, the *Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group consists of the dry dual oscillator "LD Iheardulike5ths", "LD Postmodern Talking", "SQ Busy Lines", and "SY Runtheharm" default Serum presets. These final four presets also use intense modulations on top of their use of dual oscillators.

Since five different effects are supported by the system, there are 32 different combinations possible when applying a minimum of zero and a maximum of five effects to an input audio signal. For each of these combinations, *RenderMan* [5] is used to render and save 4000 mono audio clips. Parameters are sampled randomly and uniquely from the permissible values shown in Table 4.1 and effect order when multiple effects are used is randomized.

All audio samples are played and rendered for one second using a MIDI pitch of C4, maximum note velocity, and a sampling rate of 44,100 Hz. This process is repeated for each of the 12 presets resulting in 128,000 audio clips per preset, 384,000 audio clips per preset group, and 1.536M audio clips total. Only a single C4 pitch is sampled due to the inclusion of high quality timbre-preserving pitch shifting algorithms in all commonly used digital audio workstations, thus allowing users to easily warp a desired sound they would like to use as input to the system to C4. This preprocessing step could also be done by the system automatically.

4.2.2 Audio Preprocessing

Audio clips are converted to Mel spectrograms using a short-time Fourier transform with a hop length of 512 samples, a fast Fourier transform window length of 2048, a minimum and maximum frequency of 20 Hz and 16 kHz respectively, and a Mel filter-bank of size 128. For each spectrogram the first 30 Mel-frequency cepstral coefficients, representing the smoothed spectral envelope, are also computed and saved. Lastly, each spectrogram is converted to decibels (dB). Both spectrograms and cepstra are used in order to provide the subsequent neural networks as much volume, pitch, timbre, and temporal information as possible. Early prototypes of the system using only spectral or cepstral features benefited from including both.

4.3 Modeling

SerumRNN consists of an ensemble of models that work together to take iterative steps to transform some input audio towards the timbre of some target audio. First, an *effect selection model* determines which effect to apply next and then a collection of five *effect parameter models*, one per supported effect, program the synthesizer accordingly. Figures 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5, 4.6, 4.7, and 4.8 depict the series of actions taken by the entire system to apply two audio effects to some input audio (defined as the system taking two steps).

Figure 4.2: **Step 1 Part 1:** Input the current audio and target audio MFCCs and Mel spectrograms as two-channel matrices into the effect selection model. It outputs a probability distribution for the next effect to be applied.

Model components are dashed rectangles, inputs are blue, outputs are red, and the Serum synthesizer is green. Dotted arrows represent the conceptual flow of the system and solid arrows represent the flow of tensors.

Figure 4.3: **Step 1 Part 2:** Using the next effect probability distribution, select an effect parameter model that has not been applied before and has the highest corresponding probability (in this example the distortion effect has the highest probability).

Figure 4.4: **Step 1 Part 3:** Take the most current step from the input sequences (at this point the initial input) and feed it through the distortion effect parameter model. Program Serum with the resulting effect parameter values and render Serum to obtain the next step's audio. Preprocess this audio to obtain the next step's Mel spectrogram and MFCCs.

Figure 4.5: **Step 2 Part 1:** Append the next step’s Mel spectrogram and MFCCs to the input sequences. One step has now been completed and the entire cycle can now be repeated. Input the Mel spectrogram and MFCC sequences into the effect selection model which outputs a probability distribution for the next effect to be applied.

Figure 4.6: **Step 2 Part 2:** Using the next effect probability distribution, select an effect parameter model that has not been applied before and has the highest corresponding probability (in this example the equalizer effect now has the highest probability).

Figure 4.7: **Step 2 Part 3:** Take the most current step from the input sequences (in this example the audio rendered after applying the distortion effect in Step 1) and feed it through the equalizer effect parameter model. Program Serum with the resulting effect parameter values and render Serum to obtain the next step's audio. Preprocess this audio to obtain the next step's Mel spectrogram and MFCCs.

Figure 4.8: **Step 3 Part 1:** Append the next step's Mel spectrogram and MFCCs to the input sequences. Two steps have now been completed.

4.3.1 Effect Parameter Models

The output values of effect parameter models are used to program the parameters of an effect. They take two tensors as input: a Mel spectrogram and the corresponding first 30 MFCCs. Both of these tensors consist of two channels, the first representing the input audio and the second representing the target audio. The MFCC tensor is normalized by feeding it through a batch normalization layer that has learnable shift and scale parameters. Two almost identical convolutional neural networks (CNNs) are used to extract features from each input. The Mel spectrogram CNN consists of three convolutional layers each with a 3x3 stride, 4x4 max-pool layer, and 64, 128, and 128 filters respectively. The MFCCs CNN is identical except, due to the smaller X input dimension, it uses 2x4 max-pool layers. The final max-pool layers of the two CNNs are flattened and concatenated together. This is then followed by two 128-dimensional fully connected (FC) layers with a dropout rate [66] of 50% each. All layers use ELU activations [67].

The output layers and loss functions of an effect parameter model vary depending on what effect is being modeled. Continuous parameters of an effect, where N is the number of continuous parameters, are represented as a single N -dimensional fully connected layer with a linear activation. Categorical parameters of an effect, where C is the number of classes, are each represented as a C -dimensional fully connected layer with a softmax activation. All output layers are connected to the second fully connected layer.

As a result, the effect parameter models for the compressor, EQ, phaser, and hall reverb effects have a single 3-dimensional continuous output layer and the distortion model has two output layers: a 12-dimensional categorical output layer and a 1-dimensional continuous output layer. The architecture of the distortion effect parameter model is shown in Figure 4.9 and the architecture for the other four effects is shown in Figure 4.10.

4.3.2 Effect Selection Model

The effect selection model outputs a probability distribution of what effect should be applied next to the input audio. As shown in Figures 4.2 to 4.8, it takes as input three sequences of the same length corresponding to the number of steps that have been taken by the system. The first two are sequences consisting of effect parameter model inputs: Mel spectrograms and MFCCs. The third is a sequence of 6-dimensional one-hot vectors representing which effect was applied to the input audio at each step. The first five dimensions of the one-hot vector correspond to the five supported effects and the last dimension indicates the initial step of the system when no effect has been applied yet to the input audio.

Features are extracted from the Mel spectrogram and MFCC sequences using time distributed CNNs (shown in Figure 4.11) identical in architecture to the ones in the effect parameter models, except each convolutional layer uses only half as many filters and there is only one fully connected layer which is the output. The extracted feature vectors are then concatenated with the one-hot vector effect sequence and are then fed through a 128-dimensional bi-directional long short-term memory (LSTM) layer. This is followed by a 128-dimensional fully connected layer with an ELU activation and 50% dropout applied to it, and lastly a 5-dimensional fully connected output layer with a softmax activation.

Figure 4.9: Distortion effect parameter model architecture (not to scale).

Figure 4.10: Compressor, equalizer, phaser, and hall reverb effect parameter model architecture (not to scale).

Figure 4.11: Effect selection model feature extraction time distributed CNN architecture (not to scale).

4.3.3 Training

One effect parameter model is trained per effect for each preset group (therefore 15 in total) on the Cartesian product of all possible input audio and target audio Mel spectrogram and MFCC pairs. This results in each model being trained on approximately 1.2M data points. Categorical output layers are trained with categorical cross-entropy loss and continuous output layers are trained with mean squared error loss. Multiple losses due to multiple output layers, such as for the distortion effect parameter model, are weighted equally and a batch size of 128 is used.

One effect selection model is trained for each preset group (therefore three in total) on unique sequences consisting of one to five steps (applied effects) generated randomly from the available audio clip Mel spectrograms and MFCCs. To encourage efficiency, each effect can only be applied once to the input audio. Consequently, the shortest generated sequence is of length two since this represents the original input audio and one effect being applied and similarly, the longest generated sequence is of length six which represents the original input audio and the five supported effects being applied. Approximately 500k data points are generated for each preset group effect selection model. A categorical cross-entropy loss is used for training along with a batch size of 32.

All models are trained for 100 epochs with early stopping (8 epochs of patience) and a validation and test split of 0.10 and 0.05 respectively. The Adam optimizer [68] is used with a learning rate of 0.001.

4.4 Evaluation

The system is evaluated at three levels of granularity: the effect parameter models, the effect selection models, and the entire system / ensemble of models as a whole. Each of the three preset groups are evaluated separately and yield very similar and consistent results. Detailed results are displayed for the most challenging preset group, *Advanced Modulating Shapes*, and the figures and tables for the other two preset groups can be found in Appendix A and Appendix B. Since understanding how perceptually close two audio samples are from metrics alone is difficult, audio examples for *SerumRNN* can be listened to at https://bit.ly/serum_rnn.

4.4.1 Audio Similarity Metrics

In order to effectively evaluate the system, the distance between two audio clips needs to be computed; specifically the similarity between their timbres. A variety of six different metrics is made use of to evaluate the models vigorously.

MSE, MAE, and LSD

The first three metrics are quite basic: the mean squared error (MSE), mean absolute error (MAE), and log-spectral distance (LSD) between two magnitude spectrograms. LSD is defined as the average root mean square difference between each frame of two log power spectrograms.

$$MSE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n (S_{ij} - \hat{S}_{ij})^2 \quad (4.1)$$

$$MAE = \frac{1}{mn} \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_{j=1}^n |S_{ij} - \hat{S}_{ij}| \quad (4.2)$$

$$LSD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{j=1}^m (S_{ij} - \hat{S}_{ij})^2} \quad (4.3)$$

S is an output decibel Mel spectrogram matrix, \hat{S} is the target decibel Mel spectrogram matrix, m is the number of Mel filters, and n is the number of frames.

MFCCD

The fourth metric (MFCCD) is the mean Euclidean distance between the first 30 MFCCs which represent the smoothed spectral envelope of an audio clip.

$$MFCCD = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \|C_i - \hat{C}_i\|_2 \quad (4.4)$$

C is a matrix of the first 30 output audio MFCCs for each frame, \hat{C} is a matrix of the first 30 target audio MFCCs for each frame, and n is the number of frames.

PCC

The Pearson Correlation Coefficient (PCC) can also be used to measure audio reconstruction quality [41] and is defined as

$$PCC = \frac{cov(x, y)}{\sigma_x \sigma_y} \quad (4.5)$$

where x and y are 1-dimensional vectors, not matrices. This metric is applied to decibel Mel spectrogram matrices S and \hat{S} by flattening each one using row concatenation.

MSSMAE

The last and most robust metric is based off a multi-scale spectral loss [25] that has been modified and is given the name multi-scale spectral mean absolute error (MSSMAE). Given an output audio clip and a target audio clip, magnitude spectrograms (S_i and \hat{S}_i respectively) are calculated for several different FFT sizes i . Then $\log S_i$ and $\log \hat{S}_i$ is also computed and the metric is then defined as

$$MSSMAE = \frac{1}{w} \sum_i (MAE(S_i, \hat{S}_i) + \alpha MAE(\log S_i, \log \hat{S}_i)) \quad (4.6)$$

where w is the number of different FFT sizes, α is a constant scaling term, and MAE is defined in Equation 4.2 as the mean squared error between two spectrograms. α is set to 0.1 in the experiments to make the two MAE values roughly equal since the log values are generally around one order of magnitude larger. FFT sizes of (64, 128, 256, 512, 1024, 2048) are used making $w = 6$ and the neighboring frames in the resulting spectrograms have 75% overlap. By calculating multiple regular and logarithmic spectrograms with different FFT sizes, two audio clips can be compared along different spatial-temporal resolutions.

For the MSE, MAE, LSD, MFCCD, and MSSMAE metrics, lower values indicate a higher similarity between two audio clips whereas the opposite is true for PCC values. MSE, MAE, PCC, and MSSMAE values are multiplied by 100 for better readability.

4.4.2 Effect Parameter Models

Effect parameter models are evaluated using the six metrics defined in Section 4.4.1 on 1000 input and target audio pairs from their corresponding test data sets. One can observe from Tables 4.2, A.1, and B.1 that for almost every metric and effect, the models substantially decrease the distance between the input audio clip and the target audio clip.

It is worth noting that this trend appears to be less dramatic for the phaser effect, but can be explained by the fact that spectrograms and cepstra do not represent phase information well [25]. As a result, the error metrics might be less representative of the phaser effect when compared to the other effects. For example, in some specific cases it is possible for a positive error Δ to occur even when the output audio clearly sounds much closer to the target audio than the input audio does.

Table 4.2: Effect parameter models evaluation metrics (*Adv. Mod. Shapes* preset group).

Effect	Metric	Mean Error against Target Audio			
		Input Audio	Output Audio	Δ	$\Delta\%$
<i>Compressor</i>	MSE	1.86	0.82	-1.04	-56.06
	MAE	10.50	6.43	-4.07	-38.75
	LSD	10.04	6.52	-3.53	-35.10
	MFCCD	108.53	64.48	-44.05	-40.59
	PCC	82.01	86.85	4.84	5.90
	MSSMAE	71.64	45.57	-26.07	-36.39
<i>Distortion</i>	MSE	4.49	0.78	-3.71	-82.66
	MAE	14.57	6.21	-8.36	-57.40
	LSD	13.90	6.41	-7.50	-53.92
	MFCCD	146.04	59.76	-86.29	-59.08
	PCC	74.67	80.42	5.75	7.70
	MSSMAE	94.33	65.35	-28.97	-30.72
<i>Equalizer</i>	MSE	1.48	0.80	-0.68	-45.92
	MAE	8.76	6.29	-2.47	-28.24
	LSD	8.64	6.49	-2.14	-24.82
	MFCCD	92.52	64.17	-28.35	-30.64
	PCC	84.90	86.45	1.55	1.82
	MSSMAE	64.05	64.55	0.50	0.78
<i>Phaser</i> ¹	MSE	0.86	0.77	-0.09	-10.15
	MAE	6.89	6.31	-0.58	-8.44
	LSD	7.06	6.59	-0.47	-6.67
	MFCCD	72.50	64.42	-8.08	-11.14
	PCC	86.05	85.58	-0.47	-0.55
	MSSMAE	51.53	47.33	-4.20	-8.16
<i>Hall Reverb</i>	MSE	1.28	0.48	-0.80	-62.60
	MAE	8.32	4.89	-3.44	-41.28
	LSD	8.32	5.04	-3.28	-39.43
	MFCCD	80.49	46.21	-34.28	-42.59
	PCC	83.87	89.47	5.60	6.68
	MSSMAE	60.87	38.56	-22.31	-36.65

¹Phaser specific details are provided in Section 4.4.2.

4.4.3 Effect Selection Model

The effect selection model, in this section referred to as *SerumRNN*, is compared against two baselines to showcase the advantage of 1: using an iterative system and 2: considering the order of effects.

The first baseline is a non-iterative version of the effect selection model (called *SerumRNN NI*) that uses an identical architecture and training process except that only the first step (the original input and target audio) of the Mel spectrogram and MFCC input sequences is used. As a result, the sequence of effects to be applied to the input audio can be predicted all at once using *SerumRNN NI* without iteratively modifying the audio in between steps using the effect parameter models.

The second baseline is the effect parameter model CNN with a 5-dimensional fully connected output layer and a sigmoid activation. It is trained with a binary cross-entropy loss to predict all effects at once without considering order. This baseline is called *SerumCNN*.

The accuracy of all three models for effect sequences of length one to five is measured using their test data sets of approximately 25k data points and is summarized in Tables 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5. One can observe that all three models perform remarkably well, with *SerumRNN* outperforming the other two for virtually all cases. Since the RNN models predict effects one by one, it is reasonable to come to the conclusion that accuracy is highest for the first and last step due to the first step representing the most dramatic difference between input and target audio clips and the last step being deducible given the previous effects (since repeated effects are not supported). The behavior of *SerumCNN* is also expected: accuracy decreases the longer the effect sequence is since more effects need to be predicted correctly.

Table 4.3: Effect selection models prediction accuracy (*Adv. Mod. Shapes* preset group).

Effect Selection Model	Step Number (Number of Effects for <i>SerumCNN</i>)					All
	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>SerumRNN</i>	0.994	0.984	0.983	0.979	0.999	0.985
<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	0.992	0.974	0.961	0.962	1.000	0.971
<i>SerumCNN</i>	0.993	0.975	0.946	0.916	0.889	0.955

Table 4.4: Effect selection models prediction accuracy (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Effect Selection Model	Step Number (Number of Effects for <i>SerumCNN</i>)					All
	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>SerumRNN</i>	0.993	0.983	0.981	0.986	0.994	0.985
<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	0.990	0.968	0.959	0.966	1.000	0.969
<i>SerumCNN</i>	0.992	0.968	0.941	0.921	0.909	0.952

Table 4.5: Effect selection models prediction accuracy (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Effect Selection Model	Step Number (Number of Effects for <i>SerumCNN</i>)					All
	1	2	3	4	5	
<i>SerumRNN</i>	0.992	0.983	0.983	0.974	1.000	0.983
<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	0.991	0.970	0.954	0.971	1.000	0.969
<i>SerumCNN</i>	0.990	0.963	0.936	0.913	0.884	0.947

4.4.4 Ensemble / Entire System

Similarly to the effect parameter models, the entire ensemble of models (referred to as *SerumRNN*) is evaluated using the six metrics defined in Section 4.4.1 on 1000 input and target audio pairs. These pairs are sampled from the unseen test sets and the target audio is the result of a sequence of one to five effects (200 audio pairs per sequence length) being applied to the input audio. Inference time for the entire system (audio processing, effect selection, parameter programming, and audio rendering) on a 2016 MacBook Pro laptop is approximately 300 ms per effect applied to the input audio.

Baselines

SerumRNN is compared against five baselines. The first is *SerumRNN NI* from Section 4.4.3 which enables testing for any gains obtained from using an iterative system. The second is *SerumCNN*, also from Section 4.4.3, which enables testing for any gains obtained from considering the order of effects.

The next baseline is a perfect effect selection model (*Oracle*) that always selects the "correct" next effect as is defined by the effect sequence that created the target audio. This allows the systems to be compared against what should be the technically "correct" solution. In order to test the benefit of using an effect selection model in the first place, there is also a *Random* baseline which simply chooses a random effect each time it is called. Finally, to test the benefit of applying the effect parameter models iteratively, a baseline called *SerumCNN 1S* is included. This baseline is identical to the *SerumCNN* baseline except that the effect parameter models are applied all at once to the input audio (after all effects have been predicted at once by *SerumCNN*). This results in a one-shot system with the fastest inference time possible, but no intermediate steps. This baseline is also the most similar to existing neural network synthesizer programming architectures of prior works in related literature [41, 40].

All six systems use the same five effect parameter models for each preset group. Since repeated effects are not supported, if an effect selection model chooses an effect that has already been applied in a previous step, the next most probable unused effect is selected. As a result, all systems terminate at the latest after applying the maximum of five supported effects.

Stopping Condition

Before the systems can be evaluated, a stopping condition must be defined for *SerumRNN*, *SerumRNN NI*, *SerumCNN*, and *Random*. Otherwise five effects will always be applied to the input audio, even when the target audio was created using only one effect. A reasonable stopping condition to use is terminating the system once it makes a mistake, i.e. when the distance between the input and target audio increases. However, there may be situations where making a "mistake" is advantageous since the ideal sequence of steps to the target audio can be non-monotonic. Figures 4.12, A.1, and B.1 investigate how the number of tolerated bad steps affects the resulting overall error reduction of each system. From the plotted results one can conclude that the ideal stopping condition is tolerating one step in the wrong direction before terminating.

Figure 4.12: Relationship between the tolerated number of mistake steps vs. the overall error Δ against the target audio (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Table 4.6 is the most important evaluation table and summarizes the evaluation results of *SerumRNN* and all five baselines for all three preset groups. Tables 4.7, 4.8, 4.9, 4.10, 4.11, and 4.12 give more granular evaluation details for *SerumRNN* and the five baselines for the *Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group. Appendices A and B contain the same more granular evaluation data for the *Advanced Shapes* and *Basic Shapes* preset groups respectively.

Table 4.6: Comparison of the overall mean error reduction for all systems.

Preset Group	System	Mean Error Δ against Target Audio					
		MSE	MAE	LSD	MFCCD	PCC	MSSMAE
<i>Advanced</i>	<i>Oracle</i>	-4.02	-9.45	-8.48	-97.14	14.80	-28.67
<i>Modulating</i>	<i>SerumRNN</i>	-4.04	-9.41	-8.36	-96.17	15.53	-32.53
<i>Shapes</i>	<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	-4.02	-9.20	-8.25	-94.55	15.26	-30.06
	<i>SerumCNN</i>	-3.97	-9.21	-8.18	-93.72	14.71	-28.84
	<i>Random</i>	-3.33	-7.45	-6.52	-74.40	11.96	-25.55
	<i>SerumCNN 1S</i>	-3.96	-9.12	-8.10	-92.68	14.51	-28.50
<i>Advanced</i>	<i>Oracle</i>	-2.96	-8.09	-7.21	-83.01	15.90	-37.74
<i>Shapes</i>	<i>SerumRNN</i>	-2.97	-8.08	-7.17	-83.34	16.87	-41.24
	<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	-2.96	-7.98	-7.07	-81.80	16.79	-39.14
	<i>SerumCNN</i>	-2.92	-7.84	-7.05	-81.21	15.84	-38.89
	<i>Random</i>	-2.48	-6.39	-5.71	-65.95	14.20	-35.18
	<i>SerumCNN 1S</i>	-2.88	-7.65	-6.83	-78.40	15.55	-37.80
<i>Basic Shapes</i>	<i>Oracle</i>	-4.00	-9.49	-8.19	-92.12	18.78	-41.16
	<i>SerumRNN</i>	-4.08	-9.62	-8.35	-94.08	20.03	-42.32
	<i>SerumRNN NI</i>	-3.79	-9.02	-7.75	-86.36	19.23	-40.67
	<i>SerumCNN</i>	-3.45	-8.50	-7.25	-81.01	19.32	-41.95
	<i>Random</i>	-3.14	-7.20	-6.21	-69.70	15.14	-35.30
	<i>SerumCNN 1S</i>	-3.56	-8.52	-7.36	-82.60	18.93	-40.06

Table 4.7: Evaluation metrics for the *Oracle* baseline (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	4.95	0.93	-4.02	-81.25	-1.92	-1.08	-1.38	-0.72	-0.64
MAE	16.43	6.98	-9.45	-57.54	-3.76	-2.90	-3.58	-2.08	-2.02
LSD	15.57	7.09	-8.48	-54.46	-3.52	-2.47	-3.12	-1.91	-1.77
MFCCD	167.23	70.08	-97.14	-58.09	-38.37	-29.42	-36.91	-21.97	-21.50
PCC	68.44	83.23	14.80	21.62	2.65	5.62	7.37	5.28	5.58
MSSMAE	83.29	54.62	-28.67	-34.42	3.38	-14.84	-28.13	-11.19	5.84

Table 4.8: Evaluation metrics for *SerumRNN* (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	4.97	0.94	-4.04	-81.19	-2.64	-0.86	-0.38	-0.16	-0.10
MAE	16.47	7.06	-9.41	-57.11	-5.49	-2.30	-1.13	-0.48	-0.33
LSD	15.59	7.23	-8.36	-53.63	-5.04	-1.95	-0.97	-0.41	-0.27
MFCCD	167.52	71.35	-96.17	-57.41	-56.37	-23.26	-11.41	-5.12	-3.19
PCC	68.48	84.01	15.53	22.68	5.81	6.23	2.37	1.33	1.53
MSSMAE	83.38	50.85	-32.53	-39.02	-3.70	-15.63	-9.47	-3.81	-2.23

Table 4.9: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumRNN NI* baseline (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.00	0.98	-4.02	-80.37	-2.42	-0.84	-0.48	-0.31	-0.14
MAE	16.51	7.30	-9.20	-55.76	-5.08	-1.98	-1.35	-0.86	-0.46
LSD	15.63	7.38	-8.25	-52.78	-4.59	-1.78	-1.19	-0.74	-0.44
MFCCD	167.98	73.43	-94.55	-56.28	-51.74	-20.48	-13.90	-9.07	-5.06
PCC	68.36	83.62	15.26	22.32	4.74	6.10	3.20	1.74	1.32
MSSMAE	83.23	53.18	-30.06	-36.11	-5.51	-8.48	-9.44	-6.37	-4.58

Table 4.10: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN* baseline (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	4.98	1.01	-3.97	-79.80	-2.07	-0.92	-0.68	-0.36	-0.15
MAE	16.47	7.25	-9.21	-55.96	-4.25	-2.13	-1.90	-1.05	-0.48
LSD	15.60	7.42	-8.18	-52.45	-3.93	-1.85	-1.59	-0.92	-0.42
MFCCD	167.62	73.90	-93.72	-55.91	-43.54	-21.58	-18.90	-10.82	-4.74
PCC	68.45	83.16	14.71	21.49	3.84	4.95	4.45	2.65	1.19
MSSMAE	83.33	54.49	-28.84	-34.61	-1.16	-12.47	-8.54	-6.24	-5.20

Table 4.11: Evaluation metrics for the *Random* baseline (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	4.99	1.66	-3.33	-66.71	-0.84	-0.95	-0.85	-0.81	-0.69
MAE	16.49	9.05	-7.45	-45.15	-1.70	-2.00	-1.98	-1.99	-1.89
LSD	15.62	9.10	-6.52	-41.72	-1.47	-1.74	-1.78	-1.70	-1.69
MFCCD	167.81	93.41	-74.40	-44.34	-16.85	-19.98	-19.84	-19.26	-19.53
PCC	68.24	80.20	11.96	17.52	1.73	3.72	3.85	4.00	4.15
MSSMAE	83.16	57.60	-25.55	-30.73	-4.04	-6.34	-7.63	-5.91	-8.74

Table 4.12: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN 1S* baseline (*Advanced Modulating Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	4.99	1.04	-3.96	-79.20	-2.07	-0.93	-0.65	-0.38	-0.15
MAE	16.51	7.39	-9.12	-55.26	-4.27	-2.12	-1.73	-1.13	-0.50
LSD	15.62	7.52	-8.10	-51.86	-3.91	-1.86	-1.51	-0.97	-0.39
MFCCD	167.96	75.28	-92.68	-55.18	-43.54	-21.75	-17.38	-11.71	-4.71
PCC	68.39	82.89	14.51	21.21	3.78	4.95	4.05	3.00	1.07
MSSMAE	83.51	55.01	-28.50	-34.13	-1.35	-9.00	-10.41	-7.38	-5.97

4.5 Discussion (System 1)

From Table 4.6 it is clear that all six evaluated systems significantly reduce the error between the input and target audio which indicates that the effect parameter models individually are robust and highly effective, even when applied in a random order. The author believes using two channel Mel spectrogram and MFCC inputs and training on the Cartesian product of possible input and target audio combinations (as explained in Section 4.3.1) helped achieve this robustness.

Perhaps unsurprisingly, *SerumRNN* consistently outperforms *SerumRNN NI*, *SerumCNN*, and *SerumCNN 1S* for all metrics. This highlights the importance of considering the order of effects and using an iterative approach for both effect selection and effect parameter programming. Performance of the one-shot *SerumCNN 1S* system is also quite good considering it is up to five times faster than any of the other systems. If inference speed is critically important, a reasonable compromise can be made by choosing to use this system instead.

One can also notice that for *SerumRNN* all five steps reduce the error between the input and target audio clips, with the largest gains achieved in the first two steps and the smallest in the final two steps (Tables 4.8, A.3, and B.3). In contrast to this, for the *Random* baseline (Tables 4.11, A.6, and B.6) error reduction is distributed essentially evenly between the five steps. This evenly distributed error is also seen to a lesser extent for the *Oracle* baseline (Tables 4.7, A.2, and B.2) since it also uses a fixed sequence of effects that may not have been applied in order of greatest change to the input sound. This indicates that the effect selection model chooses the effects in order of importance for multi-effect sequences, where importance is defined as the amount of change an audio effect has on a sound's Mel spectrum and cepstral coefficients. This means the intermediate steps of *SerumRNN* are educational for the user and highlight the effects with the biggest impact on the input sound first.

The most surprising result is that *SerumRNN* consistently outperforms the *Oracle* baseline, especially for the most robust MSSMAE metric. This implies that *SerumRNN* sometimes chooses effects in an order that is more optimal for the effect parameter models than using the original effect order that created the target audio. This is exciting because it suggests that the neural architecture with an ensemble of models is able to extrapolate and discover solutions outside of the scope of what would be considered "correct" by the training data. Models for estimating parameter values, like the effect parameter models of *SerumRNN*, are required for any system that attempts to automatically program VST synthesizers and / or audio effects. Since these models can never be perfect, *SerumRNN* and its iterative approach most likely provides the flexibility required to fix mistakes made by the effect parameter models and reduces pressure on them to make large changes to the input audio at later steps in the audio effects chain.

From an auditory point of view, the reduction in error for each step of *SerumRNN* can be heard very clearly with the final output audio often being indistinguishable from the target audio. The author highly recommends listening to the audio examples at https://bit.ly/serum_rnn.

Chapter 5

System 2: *LH3BDVAE*

5.1 Overview

System 2 is a tool that can generate musical notes which can then be fed to any synthesizer to be rendered as audio. It is called *LH3BDVAE* and it outputs sequences of MIDI notes for four instruments:

1. Lead instrument (monophonic)
2. Harmony instrument (polyphonic)
3. Bass instrument (monophonic)
4. Drums (polyphonic)

These sequences can be created continuously such that a single stream of music can be generated indefinitely. An existing MIDI file can also be fed to the system to initialize it and continue generating notes in that particular style. Finally, the music output by *LH3BDVAE* can be directly controlled by the user along 18 different dimensions:

- Chord progression (1 dimension)
- Mean note pitch of lead, harmony, and bass instruments (3 dimensions)
- Mean note density for each instrument (4 dimensions)
- Harmoniousness of the lead and bass instruments (2 dimensions)
- Note velocity expressiveness for each instrument (4 dimensions)
- Note microtiming expressiveness for each instrument (4 dimensions)

All of these properties of *LH3BDVAE* are achieved by implementing it using a conditional hierarchical variational autoencoder and training it on a large dataset of diverse MIDI files from which conditioning vectors are calculated for each of the 18 controllable dimensions.

5.2 Data Collection

Similarly to System 1, data collection and processing systems once again represent a significant portion of the software engineering required for *LH3BDVAE*. Data is collected by heavily preprocessing open source MIDI file datasets into individual data points that can then be fed downstream to train a conditional hierarchical variational autoencoder neural network. Details about the MIDI protocol and musical structure in general can be found in Sections 1.1.7 and 1.1.8.

5.2.1 MIDI Datasets

Unfortunately, a lot of MIDI data is proprietary or not available in the public domain, making it difficult to acquire the amount of data points required for training a typical deep neural network. Many MIDI datasets consist of a specific type of music (for example classical piano) or are completely monophonic, making them poorly suited for a tool designed to capture a wide variety of different styles and polyphonic melodies. However, there do exist three large, publicly available datasets relevant to this task:

- Lakh MIDI Dataset [69]: a collection of 176,581 unique MIDI files
- Reddit MIDI Dataset¹: a collection of 130,000 MIDI files crawled from the internet.
- Reddit Drum Percussion MIDI Archive²: a collection of 800,000 percussion only MIDI files crawled from the internet.

After preprocessing using the steps outlined in Section 5.2.3, the Reddit MIDI Dataset is determined to be a subset of the Lakh MIDI Dataset. As a result, only the Lakh MIDI Dataset is used going forward. While the Reddit Drum Percussion MIDI Archive is not useful for training a model to generate melodies since it only contains percussion MIDI files, it becomes an important asset for enabling more specialized artistic applications of *LH3BDVAE* outlined in Section 5.5.2.

5.2.2 Data Representation

Before the Lakh MIDI Dataset can be preprocessed to prepare it for training an *LH3BDVAE* model, a data representation that can be fed as input to the model needs to be defined. Two different data representations are investigated: *LHBD* and *LH3BD*. These two representations can be thought of as a hybrid of the two data representations used by the trios configuration of *MusicVAE* [49] and *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] outlined in the Related Works Section 2.5.

LHBD

The first representation that is considered is called *LHBD* and consists of transforming MIDI files into four instruments: two monophonic tracks for a lead and a bass instrument (similar to the trios configuration of *MusicVAE* [49], but with velocity and microtiming information) and two polyphonic tracks for a harmony and drums instrument (similar to a *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] limited to only two tracks). This data representation can be formalized using the following variables:

¹https://www.reddit.com/r/datasets/comments/3akhxy/the_largest_midi_collection_on_the_internet/

²https://www.reddit.com/r/WeAreTheMusicMakers/comments/3anwu8/the_drum_percussion_midi_archive_800k/

B is the number of musical bars supported and is the same for each of the four instruments

Q is the resolution of each bar (number of subdivisions per bar for quantization)

$T = B * Q$ where T is the length of each track

P is the range of MIDI note pitches supported by the lead, harmony, and bass instruments

$N = P + 2$ where N is the total number of note events supported by monophonic instruments (all MIDI note pitches plus one note for rests and one note for the note off event)

$M = 2P$ where M is the total number of note events supported by the harmony instrument (all MIDI note pitches and one note off event for each pitch)

D is the number of drums supported by the drum instrument

Variables B , Q , P , and D can be changed freely to allow the subsequent model to be customized for different applications and datasets, but are generally set to the following default values:

$B = 8$, eight bars of music strikes a reasonable balance between computational complexity and capturing diverse and interesting melodies

$Q = 16$, a resolution of 16 allows sequential 16th notes or slower to be captured accurately

$P = 61$, a MIDI note pitch range of [24, 84], also known as notes C1 to C6, captures more than 95% of the notes found in the Lakh MIDI Dataset

$D = 9$, a variation of the set of drums supported by *GrooveVAE* [58] is used: kick drum, snare drum, open hi-hat, closed hi-hat, low tom drum, high tom drum, ride cymbal, crash symbol, and rimshot

Combining everything together, the note information in MIDI files can be represented as the following four instruments:

1. Monophonic lead instrument consisting of a sequence of length T of integers in the range $[0, N)$
2. Polyphonic harmony instrument consisting of a binary matrix of shape T by M representing note on and note off events
3. Monophonic bass instrument consisting of a sequence of length T of integers in the range $[0, N)$
4. Polyphonic drum instrument consisting of a binary matrix of shape T by D representing note on events (note off events are not required since MIDI drum notes cannot be sustained)

Finally, note velocity and microtiming information can also be represented using the aforementioned scheme, making each of the four instruments consist of three components in total: note onset, note velocity, and note microtiming information.

LH3BD

One disadvantage of the *LHBD* data representation scheme is that the binary matrix used to represent polyphonic note on and note off events for the harmony instrument is sparse and highly imbalanced. A value of 0 (no event) is much more common than a value of 1 (note on or note off event) since typical music usually consists of only a handful of notes being played simultaneously at a time, especially if lead, bass, and drum notes have already been accounted for. One downstream effect of this phenomena is that it becomes difficult for the modeling process described in Section 5.4 to learn more complex polyphonic harmonies. Initial experiments using the *LHBD* data representation show that mostly basic and repetitive harmonies are learned using this data representation while the system struggles to capture more sophisticated harmonies.

This problem can be alleviated by using a slightly modified data representation scheme and limiting the polyphony of the harmony instrument to some positive integer A of maximum supported simultaneous notes. If this is done, the harmony instrument can be represented as A monophonic instrument tracks identical in structure to the lead and bass instruments. For the *LH3BD* data representation, A is chosen to be three since the simplest and most commonly used musical chords consist of three different notes.

As a result, the note information in MIDI files can now be represented as the following four instruments:

1. Monophonic lead instrument consisting of a sequence of length T of integers in the range $[0, N)$
2. Up to three notes polyphonic harmony instrument consisting of three monophonic tracks each consisting of a sequence of length T of integers in the range $[0, N)$
3. Monophonic bass instrument consisting of a sequence of length T of integers in the range $[0, N)$
4. Polyphonic drum instrument consisting of a binary matrix of shape T by D representing note on events (note off events are not required since MIDI drum notes cannot be sustained)

Once again, note velocity and microtiming information is represented in the same way as described in the previous section for *LHBD*.

5.2.3 MIDI File Preprocessing

A parallelizable preprocessing pipeline is built that takes MIDI files as input and outputs multiple datapoints in the *LH3BD* data representation format to create a dataset for training an *LH3BDVAE* model. The pipeline consists of the following steps:

1. Ensure MIDI file is not corrupt and can be opened
2. Ensure MIDI file is not too long or too short
3. Ensure MIDI file only uses the 4/4 time signature
4. Sort MIDI file instruments into lead, harmony, bass, and drums categories
5. Ensure MIDI file contains at least one instrument from each category
6. Quantize the notes in each track to a resolution of Q notes per bar and ignore notes with a velocity value of 0

7. Combine multiple drum instruments together into one drum instrument
8. Map all drum notes to D drums using the mapping shown in Table 5.1
9. Using a sliding window with a hop size of one bar, extract note onset, velocity, and microtiming sequences of length T from each of the four categories and combine them together to create datapoints using the *LH3BD* data representation
10. Remove datapoints with more than one bar of continuous silence
11. Deduplicate datapoints using note onset information
12. Calculate chord conditioning information for each datapoint (please see Section 5.3.1 for more details)

Step 4 of this pipeline is achieved by looking at the General MIDI program number for each MIDI instrument and calculating how many notes are played simultaneously. Percussion MIDI instruments are placed in the drum category and instruments with program numbers 33 to 40 (the bass section of General MIDI) are placed in the bass category. After this, the maximum number of simultaneous notes is calculated for the remaining instruments. Instruments with an amount of three or more simultaneous notes are placed in the harmony category and all remaining instruments are placed in the lead category. During Step 9 of the preprocessing pipeline, lead and bass instruments are converted to be monophonic and harmony instruments are converted to consist of three monophonic tracks.

Note velocity information is divided by 127 to normalize it between 0.0 and 1.0 and note microtiming information is calculated by measuring the distance between the original note and its quantized time value from Step 6. Microtiming always lies between -1.0 and 1.0 since a note can never be more than half a resolution value off (if this were the case it would be quantized a step earlier or a step later instead). An example of the microtiming of a simple drum beat can be seen in Figure 5.1. After preprocessing is complete, the Lakh MIDI Dataset yields 3,602,230 unique datapoints.

Figure 5.1: Microtiming visualization⁴ of a simple drumbeat. Quantized onsets are in yellow and the original onsets are in blue. Microtiming values are visible as the differences between the two onsets.

⁴<https://magenta.tensorflow.org/groovae>

Table 5.1: MIDI drum pitch number to nine drum categories (*D* Index) mapping.

MIDI Drum Pitch	General MIDI Description	<i>D</i> Index	<i>D</i> Description
35	Acoustic Bass Drum	0	Kick Drum
36	Electric Bass Drum	0	Kick Drum
38	Acoustic Snare	1	Snare Drum
39	Hand Clap	1	Snare Drum
40	Electric Snare	1	Snare Drum
65	High Timbale	1	Snare Drum
66	Low Timbale	1	Snare Drum
42	Closed Hi-Hat	2	Closed Hi-Hat
44	Pedal Hi-Hat	2	Closed Hi-Hat
54	Tambourine	2	Closed Hi-Hat
69	Cabasa	2	Closed Hi-Hat
70	Maracas	2	Closed Hi-Hat
73	Short Guiro	2	Closed Hi-Hat
80	Mute Triangle	2	Closed Hi-Hat
46	Open Hi-Hat	3	Open Hi-Hat
74	Long Guiro	3	Open Hi-Hat
81	Open Triangle	3	Open Hi-Hat
41	Low Floor Tom	4	Low Tom Drum
45	Low Tom	4	Low Tom Drum
47	Low-Mid Tom	4	Low Tom Drum
61	Low Bongo	4	Low Tom Drum
64	Low Conga	4	Low Tom Drum
51	Ride Cymbal 1	5	Ride Cymbal
53	Ride Bell	5	Ride Cymbal
59	Ride Cymbal 2	5	Ride Cymbal
43	High Floor Tom	6	High Tom Drum
48	Hi-Mid Tom	6	High Tom Drum
50	High Tom	6	High Tom Drum
60	High Bongo	6	High Tom Drum
63	Open High Conga	6	High Tom Drum
49	Crash Cymbal 1	7	Crash Cymbal
52	Chinese Cymbal	7	Crash Cymbal
55	Splash Cymbal	7	Crash Cymbal
57	Crash Cymbal 2	7	Crash Cymbal
58	Vibra Slap	7	Crash Cymbal
37	Side Stick	8	Rimshot
56	Cowbell	8	Rimshot
62	Mute High Conga	8	Rimshot
67	High Agogô	8	Rimshot
68	Low Agogô	8	Rimshot
75	Claves	8	Rimshot
76	High Woodblock	8	Rimshot
77	Low Woodblock	8	Rimshot

5.3 Conditioning

Conditioning is the mechanism of processing information in the context of other information that is provided through some auxiliary input. For example, a machine learning model being trained to generate images could be provided with a vector at training time describing the primary color found in each image in the training dataset. Similarly, this information could then also be provided at inference time to control the primary color of images output by the model and prevent it from generating images completely randomly. Conditioning for a model with a latent space can be described as telling the model to "factor out" certain specific information from the latent representation it learns which means the model can then be controlled independently using this "factored out" information.

With respect to *LH3BDVAE*, conditioning allows the system to be controlled independently along 18 different dimensions at once. However, in order to achieve this, conditioning information must be calculated for each dimension such that it can be provided during training time and inference time. Chords are the most complex conditioning information to calculate since they change over time and must therefore be represented as a sequence of information. However, the remaining 17 controllable dimensions are not temporal and can consequently be represented using a single scalar value.

5.3.1 Chord Inference

Chord inference is the process of determining which chord (or the absence of any chords) is being played during a specific time period of some music. This on its own is a difficult problem with active research being conducted on it by the computational creativity and music information retrieval community. However, chord information for *LH3BDVAE* is used as a method to steer the output of the model, and therefore does not have to be perfect. As long as the chord information provided contains a reasonably strong signal that allows the model to learn to differentiate different chords, it should be sufficient for enabling chords to be used as a controllable dimension.

Chord inference for datapoints in the *LH3BD* data representation format is done in the same way as for *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] using an open source chord inference library [8] built by Google Magenta. This library works by inferring chord labels using a Viterbi algorithm over a heuristically-defined probability distribution and supports a total of 97 different chords:

- No chord (1 chord)
- Major triad chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Minor triad chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Augmented triad chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Diminished triad chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Dominant-seventh tetrad (4 notes) chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Major-seventh tetrad (4 notes) chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Minor-seventh tetrad (4 notes) chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)
- Half-diminished tetrad (4 notes) chords for all pitch classes (12 chords)

The creators of *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2] note that even though the heuristic-based chord inference approach ignores many relevant features and can make basic mistakes, it still performs satisfactory for model conditioning. Furthermore, the model is even able to learn some of these ignored relevant features on its own, for example, the fact that the root note of a chord is often played by the bass instrument in a multi-instrument musical piece.

For the purpose of chord conditioning *LH3BDVAE*, all 48 tetrad chords are projected down to triads for increased simplicity, bringing down the number of chord classes used for conditioning to 49. Chords are inferred at a granularity of one bar, meaning that at most B different chords can occur in a *LH3BD* datapoint. The end result is that each datapoint in the training dataset has a corresponding chord conditioning sequence of length T consisting of one-hot vectors of size 49.

5.3.2 Note Pitch

Including note pitch as a controllable dimension of *LH3BDVAE* allows the average pitch of the generated notes of the lead, harmony, and bass instruments to be controlled independently. This conditional information is calculated by finding the average MIDI pitch value (an integer between 0 and 128) of all the notes for the lead, harmony, or bass instrument in an *LH3BD* datapoint. For the harmony instrument that consists of three monophonic sub-tracks, the notes from all three tracks are combined together first before calculating the mean value. This calculation is done for the entire training dataset and the resulting values are then normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation for each instrument respectively. The end result is three scalar numbers representing average note pitch conditional information for the lead, harmony, and bass instruments for each datapoint.

5.3.3 Note Density

Including note density as a controllable dimension of *LH3BDVAE* allows the sparsity / density of the generated notes of the lead, harmony, bass, and drums instruments to be controlled independently. This conditional information consists of the total number of notes in the lead, harmony, bass, or drums instrument in an *LH3BD* datapoint. For the lead, harmony, and bass instruments, only note on events are counted; note off events are not included. This calculation is done for the entire training dataset and the resulting values are then normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation for each instrument respectively. The end result is four scalar numbers representing note density conditional information for the lead, harmony, bass, and drums instruments for each datapoint.

5.3.4 Harmoniousness

Harmoniousness, also known as consonance in music, is the opposite of dissonance: when notes sound harsh, unpleasant, or unacceptable by a listener given the broader context of the music being listened to. Consonance is often associated with sweetness, pleasantness, and stability whereas dissonance is often associated with tension, clashing pitches, unpleasantness, and instability. While this phenomena is subjective and cannot be defined using absolute terms, if it can be approximated numerically it can then also be provided as a controllable dimension of *LH3BDVAE*.

Harmoniousness describes the interactions of multiple notes with one another and therefore by definition deals with note intervals. As a result, one heuristic that can be used to calculate it is measuring how many notes of a monophonic instrument like the lead or the bass are different from the chord being played by the harmony instrument. If many

notes being played by the lead or bass instrument are different from the notes making up the current chord, then the resulting music will probably sound more dissonant to a listener and vice versa. For this heuristic, notes with octave intervals are considered to be the same note since these types of intervals are generally considered to be harmonious.

Including harmoniousness as a controllable dimension of *LH3BDVAE* allows the consonance / dissonance of the generated notes of the lead and bass instruments to be controlled independently. This conditional information is calculated by finding the percentage of notes that are outside of the notes making up the triad chord being played at each corresponding time step in the chord conditioning sequence of an *LH3BD* datapoint. This calculation is done for the entire training dataset on the lead and bass instruments and the resulting values are then normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation for each instrument respectively. The end result is two scalar numbers representing harmoniousness conditional information for the lead and bass instruments for each datapoint.

5.3.5 Expressiveness

Musical expression can be described as the human element of performing music that involves some kind of personal response. Typically, musical expression can evoke more of an emotional connection or response from a listener. For example, simple video game music being rendered precisely by a computer often sounds robotic and artificial, whereas someone performing the same notes on an instrument like a piano can provide the listener with an entirely new experience. The difference between the music rendered by the computer and the music performed by the piano player is that a human will always introduce imperfections in the timing, dynamics, timbre, and articulation of the notes they play compared to a computer that can be consistent and exact every time. The human ear is incredibly sensitive to tiny changes like these and as a result, many different software tools are used by electronic music producers to help "humanize" computer generated notes using randomization and other techniques.

A proxy for measuring expressiveness is to look at how much the dynamics and timing of notes change. For MIDI notes, dynamics are represented with velocity values, i.e. a number between 0 and 127 indicating how loudly or quietly a note is played. Timing can be represented using microtiming, i.e. how far away a note is from its quantized position. Both velocity and microtiming representations are explained in more detail in Section 5.2.3. MIDI files with more constant velocity and microtiming values are probably less expressive since they sound more robotic and vice versa. As a result the consistency of velocity and microtiming values can be captured numerically through a metric like standard deviation.

Including expressiveness as a controllable dimension of *LH3BDVAE* allows the standard deviations for velocity and microtiming of the generated notes of the lead, harmony, bass, and drums instruments to be controlled independently. This conditional information consists of the standard deviation values for velocity and microtiming of the notes in each instrument of an *LH3BD* datapoint. For the lead, harmony, and bass instruments, only note on events are counted; note off events are not included. This calculation is done for the entire training dataset and the resulting values are then normalized by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation for each instrument respectively. The end result is eight scalar numbers representing expressiveness conditional information (velocity standard deviation and microtiming standard deviation) for the lead, harmony, bass, and drums instruments for each datapoint.

5.4 Modeling

LH3BDVAE is a conditional variational autoencoder that learns to generate MIDI notes for music consisting of four instruments: lead, harmony, bass, and drums. While its architecture is similar to *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2], it has been modified and extended in several key ways:

- *LH3BDVAE* is limited to four specific instrument categories and does not need to select instrument programs making the overall architecture more streamlined
- The polyphonic harmony instrument consists of three monophonic sub-tracks instead
- Notes are generated all at once instead of sampling autoregressively
- Velocity values are treated as continuous information and are therefore learnt using a regression loss
- Microtiming information is included and predicted at inference time
- The KL loss term is always enforced, making sampling quality a higher priority than reconstruction quality
- A 17-dimensional conditioning vector is injected into the architecture at multiple locations to enable independent control of the attributes discussed in Section 5.3

Overall, the architecture of *LH3BDVAE* is best described as a mix between the architectures of *MusicVAE* [49], *Multi-track MusicVAE* [2], and *GrooveVAE* [58] along with some of the key changes listed above and a stronger focus on conditioning and controllability by the user.

5.4.1 Conditional Variational Autoencoder

LH3BDVAE is a variational autoencoder with the encoder consisting of a recurrent neural network and the decoder consisting of a hierarchical recurrent neural network. It is a conditional variational autoencoder because it consumes 18 different types of conditional information which allows it to be controlled independently along these 18 different attributes (more details are in Section 5.3). The overall architecture of *LH3BDVAE* is shown in Figure 5.2. Background information about autoencoders, variational autoencoders, deep learning, and recurrent neural networks can be found in Sections 1.2.6, 1.2.7, 1.2.3, and 1.2.5 respectively.

Figure 5.2: Architecture of *LH3BDVAE*.

5.4.2 Encoder

The encoder of *LH3BDVAE* takes the following 20 inputs:

1. 17-dimensional conditioning vector
2. T timesteps of 49-dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 49) sequence of chord indices
3. T timesteps of N -dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 63) sequence of lead instrument note onset information
4. T timesteps of N -dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 63) sequence of harmony instrument sub-track 1 note onset information
5. T timesteps of N -dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 63) sequence of harmony instrument sub-track 2 note onset information
6. T timesteps of N -dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 63) sequence of harmony instrument sub-track 3 note onset information
7. T timesteps of N -dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 63) sequence of bass instrument note onset information
8. T by D (128 by 9) binary matrix of drum note onset information
9. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of lead instrument note velocity information
10. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 1 note velocity information
11. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 2 note velocity information
12. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 3 note velocity information
13. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of bass instrument note velocity information
14. T by D (128 by 9) floating point number matrix of drum note velocity information
15. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of lead instrument note microtiming information
16. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 1 note microtiming information
17. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 2 note microtiming information
18. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of harmony instrument sub-track 3 note microtiming information
19. Sequence of length T floating point numbers consisting of bass instrument note microtiming information
20. T by D (128 by 9) floating point number matrix of drum note microtiming information

The encoder’s architecture is quite minimal and consists of a 1024-dimensional bidirectional LSTM. All inputs except for the 17-dimensional conditioning vector are concatenated together along their second axis and fed to the bidirectional LSTM which then outputs a single embedding vector. The conditioning vector is concatenated with this embedding and the result is then sent to two 600-dimensional fully connected layers with linear activation functions that parameterize the μ and σ of the multivariate Gaussian with diagonal covariance of the VAE’s latent space (the details of this are explained in Section 1.2.7). Finally, a latent vector z is sampled using the μ and σ fully connected layers.

5.4.3 Decoder

The decoder of *LH3BDVAE* uses the same hierarchical approach as *MusicVAE* [49] except with significantly more outputs and it injects conditioning information at several locations in the architecture. A hierarchical decoder is used to improve decoding over many timesteps and improve the influence of the latent vector provided, especially as later steps of the output sequence are being generated. This is also known as the "posterior collapse" problem: where a decoder learns to ignore the latent state due to it already being sufficiently powerful enough to learn a general representation of the training data.

The decoder consists of two unidirectional 1024-dimensional LSTMs and takes the following three inputs:

1. 17-dimensional conditioning vector
2. T timesteps of 49-dimensional one-hot vectors (128 by 49) sequence of chord information
3. 600-dimensional z latent vector

The first LSTM is called the conductor by Roberts et al. [49]. It takes as input the latent vector z and the conditioning vector concatenated together and is unrolled to produce a sequence of B intermediate embedding vectors: one for each bar. Each intermediate embedding vector is then concatenated with the conditioning vector and the chord vector for its corresponding bar. This is then fed to the second LSTM which produces a sequence of Q final embedding vectors for each intermediate embedding vector. These outputs are then all concatenated together to create a sequence of length T . This sequence is split into four equal parts along the second axis to create four embedding sequences of length T : one for each instrument. The conditioning sequence for chords is then concatenated to each of these embedding sequences. Finally, 12 fully connected layers (onsets, velocity, and microtiming for each of the four instruments) are used to decode each of the four embedding sequences into onset, velocity, and microtiming values for the lead, harmony, bass, and drums instruments respectively. These fully connected layers use a linear activation function for microtiming values, a rectified linear unit (ReLU) activation function for velocity values, a sigmoid activation function for drum onset values, and a softmax activation function for all remaining instrument note onset values. As a result, the outputs of the decoder are the same as the last 18 inputs of the encoder listed in Section 5.4.2.

5.4.4 Training

For training, *LH3BDVAE* is optimized by minimizing a loss function consisting of two main components:

$$L_{\text{total}} = L_{\text{reconstruction}} + L_{\text{latent}} \quad (5.1)$$

where $L_{\text{reconstruction}}$ is the sum of the reconstruction loss for all four instruments and L_{latent} is the KL divergence between the posterior distribution $p(z | x)$ approximated by the encoder and the multivariate Gaussian with diagonal covariance prior distribution $p(z)$.

$$L_{\text{reconstruction}} = L_{\text{lead}} + L_{\text{harmony}} + L_{\text{bass}} + L_{\text{drums}} \quad (5.2)$$

$$D_{\text{KL}}(p(x) || q(x)) = \sum_x p(x) \log \frac{p(x)}{q(x)} \quad (5.3)$$

$$L_{\text{latent}} = D_{\text{KL}}(q_{\lambda}(z | x) || p(z)) \quad (5.4)$$

This KL divergence term encourages $q_{\lambda}(z | x)$ to be similar to the prior distribution $p(z)$ since the closer the two distributions are to one another, the smaller the KL divergence becomes. This ensures that the decoder produces high quality samples and can interpolate between points in the latent space well.

L_{lead} , L_{harmony} , L_{bass} , and L_{drums} can be further broken down into the sum of the reconstruction loss for note onsets, note velocities, and note microtimings. Mean squared error (MSE) is used for velocity and microtiming reconstruction loss, binary crossentropy (BCE) is used for drums note onset reconstruction loss, and categorical crossentropy (CCE) is used for all remaining instruments note onset reconstruction loss. For the harmony instrument, these reconstruction loss values are averaged across the three sub-tracks before summing them together. All of this is formalized with the following equations:

$$MSE_{1D}(S, \hat{S}) = \frac{1}{T} \sum_i^T (S_i - \hat{S}_i)^2 \quad (5.5)$$

$$MSE_{2D}(X, \hat{X}) = \frac{1}{TD} \sum_i^T \sum_j^D (X_{ij} - \hat{X}_{ij})^2 \quad (5.6)$$

$$BCE(X, \hat{X}) = \frac{1}{TD} \sum_i^T \sum_j^D (-\hat{X}_{ij} \log(X_{ij}) - (1 - \hat{X}_{ij}) \log(1 - X_{ij})) \quad (5.7)$$

$$CCE(X, \hat{X}) = -\frac{1}{T} \sum_i^T \sum_j^N \hat{X}_{ij} \log(X_{ij}) \quad (5.8)$$

$$L_{\text{lead}} = CCE(O_{\text{lead}}, \hat{O}_{\text{lead}}) + MSE_{1D}(V_{\text{lead}}, \hat{V}_{\text{lead}}) + MSE_{1D}(M_{\text{lead}}, \hat{M}_{\text{lead}}) \quad (5.9)$$

$$L_{\text{harmony}} = \frac{1}{3} \sum_n^3 CCE(O_n, \hat{O}_n) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_n^3 MSE_{1D}(V_n, \hat{V}_n) + \frac{1}{3} \sum_n^3 MSE_{1D}(M_n, \hat{M}_n) \quad (5.10)$$

$$L_{\text{bass}} = CCE(O_{\text{bass}}, \hat{O}_{\text{bass}}) + MSE_{1D}(V_{\text{bass}}, \hat{V}_{\text{bass}}) + MSE_{1D}(M_{\text{bass}}, \hat{M}_{\text{bass}}) \quad (5.11)$$

$$L_{\text{drums}} = BCE(O_{\text{drums}}, \hat{O}_{\text{drums}}) + MSE_{2D}(V_{\text{drums}}, \hat{V}_{\text{drums}}) + MSE_{2D}(M_{\text{drums}}, \hat{M}_{\text{drums}}) \quad (5.12)$$

where O , V , and M are note onset, velocity, and microtiming reconstruction values for each instrument and \hat{O} , \hat{V} , and \hat{M} are the corresponding ground truth values.

LH3BDVAE is trained for 100 epochs with early stopping (8 epochs of patience) and a validation and test split value of 0.10 and 0.05 respectively. The Adam optimizer [68] is used with a learning rate of 0.001.

5.5 Evaluation

LH3BDVAE is evaluated quantitatively on its ability to generate musical notes using several different metrics across all 20 of its outputs and qualitatively on its usefulness and extensibility as a creative and artistic tool.

5.5.1 Reconstruction and Sampling Metrics

LH3BDVAE is evaluated quantitatively on a holdout test set consisting of 5% of the *LH3BD* datapoints derived from preprocessing the Lakh MIDI Dataset [69]. This means the test set consists of 180,112 datapoints.

The sampling ability of *LH3BDVAE* is numerically measured by calculating the KL divergence between the posterior distribution $p(z | x)$ approximated by the encoder and the multivariate Gaussian with diagonal covariance prior distribution $p(z)$ using Equation 5.4 from Section 5.4.4.

The reconstruction ability of *LH3BDVAE* is evaluated by looking at the loss function values for onsets (categorical crossentropy and binary crossentropy), velocity (mean squared error), and microtiming (mean squared error) for each reconstructed instrument along with introducing several easier to interpret metrics. These metrics are accuracy for lead, harmony, and bass instrument onset values, precision / recall / F1 score for drum onset values, and mean absolute error for velocity and microtiming values. Accuracy is not a good metric for evaluating drum onset reconstruction ability since the instrument is represented using a binary matrix and the nine different drum classes are highly imbalanced.

Overall evaluation results for *LH3BDVAE* are summarized in Table 5.2, non-drum evaluation results are shown in Table 5.3, and drum related evaluation results are listed in Table 5.4.

Table 5.2: Overall evaluation metrics for *LH3BDVAE*.

L_{total}	$L_{\text{reconstruction}}$	L_{latent}
1.3763	0.9909	0.3854

Table 5.3: Lead, harmony, and bass instrument evaluation metrics for *LH3BDVAE*.

Instrument	Onset CCE	Onset Acc.	Vel. MSE	Vel. MAE	MT MSE	MT MAE
Lead	0.1750	0.9366	0.0082	0.0327	0.0120	0.0363
Harmony	0.4931	0.8384	0.0185	0.0562	0.0086	0.0310
- Sub-track 1	0.5236	0.8317	0.0207	0.0638	0.0100	0.0334
- Sub-track 2	0.4888	0.8360	0.0171	0.0517	0.0078	0.0296
- Sub-track 3	0.4671	0.8475	0.0178	0.0532	0.0081	0.0301
Bass	0.1774	0.9397	0.0077	0.0324	0.0042	0.0185

Table 5.4: Drums evaluation metrics for *LH3BDVAE*.

BCE	Precision	Recall	F1	Vel. MSE	Vel. MAE	MT MSE	MT MAE
0.0702	0.9278	0.8600	0.8926	0.0126	0.0364	0.0033	0.0158

5.5.2 Artistic Applications

LH3BDVAE is intended to be a creative tool that provides the user with an intuitive experience for exploring the possibilities of generated music. As a result, the author believes that while the numerical evaluation metrics for *LH3BDVAE* are insightful, the best way to evaluate the system is to apply it artistically and provide others the opportunity to interact with it. The system’s extensibility also becomes clear if it can be easily adapted to a variety of different use cases.

With all of this in mind, *LH3BDVAE* is integrated into and adapted for five different artistic applications. The last four applications are made possible through a collaboration with Qosmo Inc.⁵, a digital art and technology company that provided the vision, resources, and expertise for the non-*LH3BDVAE* related components of these projects.

Artistic Application 1: *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* Combined

The first application is the combination of System 1 and System 2 of this thesis to help a user learn how to program the timbre of the Serum VST synthesizer using *SerumRNN* and then inspiring the user to create music by generating notes for the synthesizer to render using *LH3BDVAE*. This application is discussed in more detail in Section 6.1.

Artistic Application 2: Controllable Music Generator

The second application is building a user interface for *LH3BDVAE* that runs in a browser and allows for continuous music to be generated indefinitely. This can be used by music producers to acquire songwriting inspiration for different chord progressions and average note pitch and density values, or simply as a device for generating background music. This application is similar to Google Magenta’s *LoFi Player* [65], except that it gives the

⁵<https://qosmo.jp/en/>

user much more fine-grained control over the generated output. The browser UI for this application can be seen in Figure 5.3.

The user interface for controlling *LH3BDVAE* in the browser is organized into several sections:

- Lead** (0770_Chaos_sf2_file):
 - Pitch: 0.00
 - Density: -0.50
 - Harmoniousness: 1.50
 - Volume: -10.00
- Harmony** (1060_FluidR3_GM_sf2_file):
 - Pitch: 0.00
 - Density: 0.00
 - Volume: -7.00
- Bass** (1160_Aspirin_sf2_file):
 - Pitch: 0.00
 - Density: -0.50
 - Harmoniousness: 1.00
 - Volume: -11.00
- Drums**:
 - Density: 0.00
 - Volume: -6.00
- Chords**: Abm7, D, Cm, Gdim (selected), Japanese
- Signal Processing**:
 - Z initial sig: 0.00
 - Z step sig: 0.00
 - Cond initial sig: 0.00
 - Cond step sig: 0.00
- Action Buttons**: Generate, Download MIDI, Play, BPM 120

Figure 5.3: User interface for controlling *LH3BDVAE* in the browser.

Artistic Application 3: Gesture-based Music Generation

Application 3 enables a user to discover the latent space of *LH3BDVAE* in an intuitive way. This is done by mapping a subset of the 600-dimensional latent space to two dimensions using a dimensionality reduction technique like t-SNE or UMAP [70]. The user's finger and a touchscreen on a smartphone can be used to "travel" through the latent space in two dimensions and listen to the resulting generated music. XY coordinates from finger presses are mapped to the nearest points from the sampled 600-dimensional latent space and then interpolated to create a z vector which is then fed to the decoder of *LH3BDVAE*. The decoder generates notes using z which are then rendered by on-device software synthesizers. Conditioning information is generated passively for simplicity and to allow a user to focus solely on exploring the latent space. Figure 5.4 shows a diagram for this application utilizing only three instruments (lead, bass, and drums).

Figure 5.4: Diagram for gesture-based control of *LH3BDVAE*.

Artistic Application 4: *Neural Beatbox*

Application 4 is probably the most artistic oriented of the five. It is an art project called *Neural Beatbox* that makes use of *LH3BDVAE* to generate drum beats and empower anyone to become creative through beatboxing. When visiting the *Neural Beatbox* website, a user first records random noises using their laptop camera. These sounds are then segmented and classified into D (see Table 5.1) different drum categories using a convolutional neural network very similar in architecture to the effect parameter models (Section 4.3.1) of *SerumRNN*. The categorized sounds are then used to render the drum notes generated by *LH3BDVAE*.

Multiple users can collaborate together over the internet and each can contribute their own unique sounds to the generated drum patterns, thus making the experience more engaging, surprising, and novel for everyone. As shown in Figure 5.5, the video the user records when making the sounds is also segmented into short clips to visualize each drum hit in an entertaining way.

Figure 5.5: Screenshots of different *Neural Beatbox* sessions.

Technically speaking, this application involves reducing *LH3BDVAE* to only the drums instrument and outputting four instead of eight bars of notes. The conditioning vector is also shortened accordingly, but increased in granularity to allow the densities, velocities, and microtimings of the D drum categories to be controlled individually. This modified architecture is then trained on the Reddit Drum Percussion MIDI Archive dataset discussed in Section 5.2.1 and allows the model to capture an incredibly diverse amount of drum beats and patterns. Small steps are taken via vector arithmetic in the latent space to ensure the generated drum beats are unique and change smoothly while modifications to the conditioning vector are made automatically to encourage specific drum categories to be generated depending on which sounds have been provided by the user(s).

Figure 5.6 provides a visualization of the two step classification and rhythm generation process that powers *Neural Beatbox*. The art project has been accepted to the NeurIPS 2020 AI Art Gallery⁶ and the "AI: More Than Human" exhibition^{7,8} at the World Museum in Liverpool, UK. More information and a video demonstration of *Neural Beatbox* can be found at <https://qosmo.jp/en/projects/neural-beatbox/> and the art project itself is located at <https://neuralbeatbox.net/>.

⁶<http://www.aiartonline.com/music-2020>

⁷<https://qosmo.jp/en/news/neuralbeatbox-worldmuseum/>

⁸<https://www.liverpoolmuseums.org.uk/whatson/world-museum/exhibition/ai-more-human>

Figure 5.6: Visualization of the sound classification and rhythm generation utilized by *Neural Beatbox*.

Artistic Application 5: *Neural Beatbox - Solo*

The final artistic application is called *Neural Beatbox - Solo* and is a non-collaborative version of *Neural Beatbox* that specializes in generating more "glitchy" and abstract drum beats. This is represented with a more distorted and dark looking user interface as can be seen in Figure 5.7.

More abstract sounding generated outputs are achieved by training *LH3BDVAE* in the same way as for *Neural Beatbox*, but with a higher amount of granularity for each bar ($Q = 24$) in order to capture more timing intricacies. After this, the encoder is used to find the latent space vectors for approximately 30 handpicked drum beat examples that together are a representative sample of the types of glitchy drum beats desired as output. These anchor points are then used to generate virtually infinite new latent vectors z through vector interpolation and random noise that can then be fed to the decoder and create the generated output of *Neural Beatbox - Solo*.

The art project has been showcased at the Nvidia GTC 2021 conference^{9,10} and is included in their "Art and Music in Light of AI" online visual art gallery¹¹. *Neural Beatbox - Solo* can be found at <https://solo.neuralbeatbox.net/>.

⁹<https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/gtc/>

¹⁰<https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/deep-learning-ai/ai-art-gallery/artists/nao-tokui-and-qosmo/>

¹¹<https://www.nvidia.com/en-us/deep-learning-ai/ai-art-gallery/>

Figure 5.7: Examples of *Neural Beatbox - Solo*'s more abstract user interface.

5.6 Discussion (System 2)

The evaluation metrics of *LH3BDVAE* in Tables 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4 indicate that the system is able to reconstruct the training data successfully, while still maintaining a reasonably low KL divergence between the posterior distribution $p(z | x)$ approximated by the encoder and the prior distribution $p(z)$. One reason for the high reconstruction capability is the extensive conditioning information for each of the four instruments provided to the model during training and inference time. This information improves reconstruction quality compared to a non-conditional variational autoencoder because it prevents the latent space from having to encode extra information, thus saving precious "space" for encoding other vital attributes not included in the conditioning information.

One can deduce from Table 5.3 that out of the non-drum instruments, note onset and velocity reconstruction is most successful for the bass, followed by the lead, and lastly the harmony. This makes sense intuitively because bass instruments tend to play a smaller range of different notes and more repetitive melodies when compared to a typically much more exciting lead instrument like a guitar or a piano. This means less information is required to represent the bass instrument in the latent space, thus making it easier for *LH3BDVAE* to reconstruct it more accurately. Similarly, the harmony instrument is polyphonic (since it consists of three monophonic tracks) and contains roughly triple the amount of notes compared to the lead instrument, making it naturally much more difficult to reconstruct given the higher level of complexity that needs to be encoded. However, a reconstruction accuracy of greater than 80% is still respectable and is sufficient for capturing diverse and interesting harmony compositions.

Note microtiming reconstruction follows a different trend, with the bass instrument still being the best, but the metrics for the harmony instrument outperforming the lead instrument. This can be explained by the fact that it is rare for harmony melodies to be more "groovy", syncopated, or expressive compared to the lead instrument since they are usually intended to accompany the lead instrument rather than take attention away from it. As a result, it is easier for *LH3BDVAE* to learn the microtiming information of the harmony instrument than the lead instrument and this is reflected in the evaluation metrics.

Table 5.4 indicates that reconstruction for the drum instrument is also quite good, with a note onset reconstruction F1 score value of 0.8926. Note onset precision is 6-7% higher than recall, but this is expected since *LH3BDVAE* is compressing all the information it is given before reconstructing the most important parts. Note velocity reconstruction is better than the harmony instrument, but worse than the lead and bass instruments. This is presumably due to drum notes having a much wider range of typical velocity values than non-drum notes, making them more difficult to reconstruct. Finally, drum note microtiming reconstruction is the best of all four instruments, most likely because drum beats have the most consistent microtiming drum patterns compared to the other instruments, making them easier to compress. In addition to this, drum notes contain no pitch information, meaning there is more "space" left in the model's capacity and latent space to encode microtiming information.

The artistic applications of *LH3BDVAE* presented in Section 5.5.2 show that it is an extensible tool with many different creative uses and can generate music through user interaction from a diverse and also non-technical audience. A high degree of control can be given to the user through a complete user interface like in the Controllable Music Generator application, or minimal but intuitive control can be provided like in the Gesture-based Music Generation, *Neural Beatbox*, and *Neural Beatbox - Solo* applications. Overall, applying *LH3BDVAE* to several novel art projects shows that not only is it a technically capable tool, but it can also inspire and engage people, especially when made accessible through art galleries that bring the technology to the general public in a delightful way.

Chapter 6

Discussion

In this chapter, *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* as complementary tools is discussed along with their corresponding limitations, ethical considerations, and areas of future work. Discussion specifically about each system and its evaluation is located in Chapter 4, Section 4.5 for *SerumRNN* and Chapter 5, Section 5.6 for *LH3BDVAE*.

6.1 *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* Combined

The objective of this thesis is to build computational creativity tools that utilize machine learning to reduce the steep learning curve beginners face when getting started with music production and VST synthesizer programming. *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* can be seen as two complementary systems that attempt to tackle this goal with *SerumRNN* addressing the sound design process and *LH3BDVAE* addressing the note composition process required for creating music with a VST synthesizer.

In order to informally assess the synergy of the two tools, five first-time music production users were invited to play with both systems at once and create a simple eight bar long track. Users were asked to choose three desired target sounds from the test dataset of *SerumRNN* to use for the lead, harmony, and bass instruments. They then went through the process of programming the Serum synthesizer once for each instrument using the intermediate steps output by *SerumRNN* and applying the appropriate audio effects. Finally, they were given control over *LH3BDVAE* through the user interface for Artistic Application 2 shown in Figure 5.3 of Section 5.5.2 to compose the notes for each track. All notes were rendered using the three programmed instances of Serum from the first step and drum notes were rendered using a set of default drum hit samples. Users could also go back and change the Serum parameters of each instrument with and without the assistance of *SerumRNN*.

While no strong conclusions can be made due to the limited number of users participating and the informal experiment setting, some general trends were observed. Users found the experience enjoyable and expressed delight in being able to create something musical so quickly with no prior background knowledge.

In general, users spent more time with *LH3BDVAE* exploring the latent space of infinitely many possible note compositions and were especially engrossed with changing the different conditioning dimensions and listening to the resulting independent changes. While users spent less time on programming the parameters of Serum through the intermediate steps output by *SerumRNN*, they were surprised at how complicated the sound design process is and how overwhelming the user interface for Serum looks. However, feedback was given that breaking the sound design process into smaller steps made it clear what each effect does to the sound and made users feel like they were programming the synthesizer, not the AI. Users would also often deviate from the suggestions provided by *SerumRNN* and customize the sound to their own liking after following the intermediate steps of *SerumRNN*

first, most likely due to them obtaining an initial understanding of what the parameters for the different audio effects do.

After this informal experiment, there is evidence to suggest that *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* can work in tandem to educate others while still enabling them to preserve a feeling of ownership over the results. The first impressions of the users also reinforces the importance of the original objectives of this thesis: creating an interpretable, step-by-step tool for sound design and a highly-controllable tool for note composition.

6.2 Limitations

While both System 1 and System 2 are quite capable for their intended purposes, they still have important limitations. Some of the limitations for *SerumRNN* are the following:

- Currently, only the Serum VST synthesizer is supported (although the entire system could be retrained on a different synthesizer)
- Only input sounds and target sounds similar to the auditory space of the 12 different synthesizer presets and five different audio effects will result in significant improvements to the input sound
- Only three parameters for each audio effect are supported for programming
- Serum’s modulation parameters and graphs cannot be programmed through the VST interface
- Phase and temporal changes in audio are difficult to learn for the system
- Stereo audio is not supported, making some effects much harder to learn
- Input and target audio are assumed to have a fundamental frequency of C4, and differently pitched inputs probably need to be re-pitched to be used by the system
- The system cannot run on Linux due to Serum being only compatible with OSX and Windows

Several of these limitations can be overcome by re-training *SerumRNN* on more synthesizer patches, and increasing its capacity to include more audio effects and programmable parameters. Audio pitch information could also be provided as an input to eliminate the C4 fundamental pitch requirement. All of these changes increase the complexity of the system and how much training data needs to be collected, meaning training times would also increase significantly.

Some of the current limitations for *LH3BDVAE* are the following:

- Only four MIDI tracks are supported
- The range of note pitches for the lead, harmony, and bass instruments is limited
- Only nine different drum types are supported and all other drum hits must be mapped to the nine categories
- Only 48 different chords for conditioning are supported
- Only music in the 4/4 time signature can be generated
- Consecutive notes faster than 16th notes cannot be encoded or generated

- Only eight bars of notes can be composed
- MIDI training data is limited and the model can only learn genres and patterns present in the training dataset

All of these limitations besides the last one can be overcome to an extent by modifying the preprocessing, architecture, and hyperparameters of *LH3BDVAE* (discussed in Section 5.2.2) and increasing its capacity with the trade-off of longer training times. With regards to generating longer sequences, there are limits to how many steps the hierarchical decoder of *LH3BDVAE* can decode without "posterior" collapse occurring [49], so approaches like *Music Transformer* [54] and *TransformerVAE* [56] are probably better suited for this.

6.3 Ethical Considerations

Combining artificial intelligence with creativity carries with it various different ethical considerations, one of which is a potential future decrease in demand for professional audio producers due to an increasing ability to replace them with technology. One way of preventing this is to build systems that are collaborative and can augment people rather than replacing them entirely. While the research presented in this thesis is just the tip of the iceberg of what is possible with intelligent music production, one can imagine a future where tools like *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* might be able to find more efficient and simpler methods for sound design and note composition, thus educating students more effectively and further democratizing music production. This can be compared to a similar situation that occurred when beat-matching technology was invented and added to DJ systems (to the disgruntlement of some DJing "purists"). However, this sometimes controversial technology democratized DJing and enabled a new generation of artists to focus on new creative applications, thus progressing the community as a whole.

Another ethical concern specific to *LH3BDVAE* is the generation of copyrighted material by the model, due to it potentially reconstructing datapoints verbatim from the training dataset. With the recent rise of large language models, this issue has become of increasing importance in the machine learning community, and it has been shown that this concern is substantiated [71]. For *LH3BDVAE* specifically, the risk of outputting copyrighted material is low due to the model's relatively small capacity (low number of parameters) and the duration of the music it outputs is only eight bars long making it more likely to fall under fair use copyright provisions. However, if the model significantly increases in capacity or is modified to output longer sequences, checks should be put in place to ensure that the training dataset does not contain any copyrighted material or that the model does not reconstruct note sequences verbatim from the training dataset. As this is an active area of research, mitigation techniques for large language models will improve over time and will almost certainly also be applicable to note composition models like *LH3BDVAE*.

6.4 Future Work

There are many areas of potential future work for both systems. As for *SerumRNN*, currently its training data is sampled randomly and thus many of the generated sounds are not useful musically. The efficiency of this process could be improved through the use of adversarial techniques or heuristics that can detect the suitability of a sound for music production. By doing this, the size of the training dataset could be reduced while making the information contained in each data point more valuable. In addition to this, the audio similarity metrics for evaluating *SerumRNN* are also not perfect and become less representative when there are large changes to the phase of a signal. This could be alleviated

by including a user study consisting of volunteers familiar with audio production who can judge how similar the target sound and final sound are to each other. *SerumRNN* could also be expanded to support more audio effects and parameters in order to make it more applicable to a wider variety of audio production processes. Finally, a user interface similar to *Magenta Studio* [13] could be developed for *SerumRNN* using Max for Live¹: a platform that enables building custom audio plugins. With a proper user interface completed, a formal user study on the usability and intuitiveness of *SerumRNN* could also be conducted and would provide valuable feedback on how to further improve the system.

With regards to *LH3BDVAE*, the system would also benefit from a formal user study measuring its practicality and user experience. Besides this, the maximum length of music that the system can generate at once is quite short and therefore it cannot capture longer term dependencies and details. As mentioned in Section 6.2, the architectures of the encoder and decoder could be migrated to a transformer [54, 56] or a similar architecture, which would enable *LH3BDVAE* to generate much longer note sequences. Finally, there are countless more art projects that *LH3BDVAE* could be incorporated into. In particular, a version of *Neural Beatbox* that also includes more outputs of *LH3BDVAE*, like the bass and lead tracks, is planned to be developed in the future.

¹<https://www.ableton.com/en/live/max-for-live/>

Chapter 7

Conclusion

In this thesis, two computational creativity tools are developed to reduce the steep learning curve beginners face when getting started with music production and VST synthesizer programming. *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* are two complementary systems with *SerumRNN* devoted to the sound design process and *LH3BDVAE* focused on the note composition process required for creating music with a VST synthesizer.

Through the experiments performed in this thesis it is demonstrated that *SerumRNN* is consistently able to produce intermediate steps that bring the input audio significantly closer to the target audio while using a fully featured, industry leading VST synthesizer. *SerumRNN* also provides near real-time, quantitative feedback about which effects are the most important for creating a target sound. In addition to this, it can also find effect sequence orders that are potentially more optimal than what the target audio was originally created with. With *SerumRNN* the user can pick and choose which intermediate steps they would like to use and can feed tweaked versions back into the system for additional fine-tuning or to learn more.

It is also demonstrated that *LH3BDVAE* is able to successfully reconstruct and generate notes for lead, harmony, bass, and drum instruments while being highly controllable by a user. The five artistic applications of *LH3BDVAE* also indicate that its controllability and simple architecture make it an extensible tool with many different creative uses. It is shown that *LH3BDVAE* can empower a diverse and often non-technical audience to generate music through intuitive user interactions.

Overall, initial user feedback indicates that *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* can work in tandem to educate music production beginners while still enabling the user to preserve a feeling of ownership over the results. This feedback on the two systems also reinforces the importance of the original objectives of the thesis: creating an interpretable, step-by-step tool for sound design and a highly-controllable tool for note composition.

The author believes this thesis is just the tip of the iceberg for building AI powered sound design tools. One can imagine a future where tools like *SerumRNN* and *LH3BDVAE* might be able to find more efficient and simpler methods for creating music, thus educating students more effectively and democratizing sound design and music production.

Appendix A

System 1 Evaluation Results: *Advanced Shapes* Preset Group

Figure A.1: Relationship between the tolerated number of mistake steps vs. the overall error Δ against the target audio (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Table A.1: Effect parameter models evaluation metrics (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Effect	Metric	Mean Error against Target Audio			
		Input Audio	Output Audio	Δ	$\Delta\%$
<i>Compressor</i>	MSE	2.27	0.87	-1.40	-61.69
	MAE	11.93	6.96	-4.97	-41.64
	LSD	11.25	6.93	-4.32	-38.41
	MFCCD	120.61	67.57	-53.03	-43.97
	PCC	74.01	83.29	9.28	12.53
	MSSMAE	75.46	46.93	-28.54	-37.82
<i>Distortion</i>	MSE	2.66	0.89	-1.76	-66.44
	MAE	11.74	6.65	-5.09	-43.34
	LSD	11.44	6.85	-4.59	-40.12
	MFCCD	113.58	62.39	-51.19	-45.07
	PCC	72.49	76.38	3.89	5.37
	MSSMAE	82.21	60.93	-21.28	-25.88
<i>Equalizer</i>	MSE	1.80	0.77	-1.02	-57.00
	MAE	10.38	6.44	-3.94	-37.96
	LSD	9.88	6.52	-3.36	-34.00
	MFCCD	104.37	62.57	-41.80	-40.05
	PCC	80.20	84.44	4.24	5.29
	MSSMAE	80.40	66.66	-13.73	-17.08
<i>Phaser</i> ¹	MSE	0.88	0.79	-0.10	-10.91
	MAE	7.09	6.43	-0.66	-9.34
	LSD	7.23	6.66	-0.57	-7.90
	MFCCD	71.75	63.66	-8.09	-11.28
	PCC	80.89	81.71	0.83	1.02
	MSSMAE	52.59	45.88	-6.71	-12.75
<i>Hall Reverb</i>	MSE	0.99	0.49	-0.50	-50.69
	MAE	7.73	5.19	-2.55	-32.93
	LSD	7.50	5.33	-2.18	-29.03
	MFCCD	71.33	47.65	-23.68	-33.20
	PCC	84.22	87.52	3.30	3.91
	MSSMAE	57.44	38.88	-18.56	-32.31

¹Phaser specific details are provided in Section 4.4.2.

Table A.2: Evaluation metrics for the *Oracle* baseline (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.93	0.97	-2.96	-75.38	-1.09	-0.97	-0.91	-0.96	-0.82
MAE	15.30	7.21	-8.09	-52.89	-3.07	-2.54	-2.62	-2.45	-2.21
LSD	14.46	7.25	-7.21	-49.84	-2.74	-2.26	-2.33	-2.16	-1.97
MFCCD	153.34	70.33	-83.01	-54.14	-31.27	-26.43	-26.95	-24.82	-22.49
PCC	64.26	80.16	15.90	24.75	5.32	4.75	5.59	5.33	6.47
MSSMAE	95.64	57.89	-37.74	-39.47	-13.80	-12.28	-11.84	-8.51	-18.02

Table A.3: Evaluation metrics for *SerumRNN* (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.92	0.95	-2.97	-75.80	-1.74	-0.76	-0.35	-0.14	-0.06
MAE	15.28	7.20	-8.08	-52.87	-4.48	-2.01	-1.13	-0.51	-0.20
LSD	14.44	7.27	-7.17	-49.64	-4.12	-1.68	-0.96	-0.45	-0.17
MFCCD	153.24	69.90	-83.34	-54.38	-46.05	-20.51	-11.57	-5.89	-2.34
PCC	64.26	81.12	16.87	26.25	7.59	5.63	2.32	1.75	1.48
MSSMAE	95.76	54.52	-41.24	-43.07	-19.55	-11.00	-5.82	-4.16	-2.29

Table A.4: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumRNN NI* baseline (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.92	0.97	-2.96	-75.40	-1.65	-0.78	-0.39	-0.16	-0.07
MAE	15.28	7.30	-7.98	-52.25	-4.14	-2.11	-1.20	-0.59	-0.30
LSD	14.44	7.37	-7.07	-48.97	-3.75	-1.83	-1.03	-0.52	-0.24
MFCCD	153.17	71.37	-81.80	-53.40	-42.48	-21.07	-12.44	-6.24	-3.52
PCC	64.25	81.04	16.79	26.13	7.70	4.40	3.04	2.18	1.99
MSSMAE	95.54	56.40	-39.14	-40.96	-16.09	-12.76	-5.91	-3.23	-3.28

Table A.5: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN* baseline (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.92	1.00	-2.92	-74.43	-0.94	-1.01	-0.67	-0.35	-0.16
MAE	15.27	7.44	-7.84	-51.31	-2.53	-2.54	-1.81	-1.05	-0.56
LSD	14.44	7.39	-7.05	-48.81	-2.46	-2.14	-1.59	-0.95	-0.50
MFCCD	153.21	71.99	-81.21	-53.01	-26.28	-25.61	-18.86	-11.53	-6.60
PCC	64.30	80.14	15.84	24.63	4.80	5.07	3.88	3.42	1.89
MSSMAE	95.46	56.56	-38.89	-40.75	-9.53	-13.58	-10.94	-4.68	-2.56

 Table A.6: Evaluation metrics for the *Random* baseline (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.93	1.45	-2.48	-63.04	-0.73	-0.75	-0.59	-0.45	-0.34
MAE	15.29	8.89	-6.39	-41.82	-1.77	-1.90	-1.57	-1.31	-1.08
LSD	14.45	8.74	-5.71	-39.49	-1.52	-1.69	-1.41	-1.15	-1.00
MFCCD	153.30	87.36	-65.95	-43.02	-17.20	-19.95	-16.30	-13.20	-12.55
PCC	64.31	78.52	14.20	22.08	2.95	3.95	4.26	5.01	3.09
MSSMAE	95.68	60.50	-35.18	-36.77	-9.53	-8.45	-8.38	-7.47	-6.27

 Table A.7: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN 1S* baseline (*Advanced Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	3.93	1.05	-2.88	-73.30	-0.85	-0.98	-0.78	-0.34	-0.13
MAE	15.28	7.62	-7.65	-50.10	-2.34	-2.34	-2.10	-1.05	-0.44
LSD	14.44	7.61	-6.83	-47.31	-2.29	-1.99	-1.80	-0.90	-0.39
MFCCD	153.23	74.83	-78.40	-51.16	-24.30	-23.48	-21.35	-11.08	-5.14
PCC	64.34	79.90	15.55	24.18	4.27	4.91	4.75	2.98	1.88
MSSMAE	95.38	57.58	-37.80	-39.63	-8.77	-14.17	-9.91	-5.41	-1.77

Appendix B

System 1 Evaluation Results: *Basic Shapes* Preset Group

Figure B.1: Relationship between the tolerated number of mistake steps vs. the overall error Δ against the target audio (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Table B.1: Effect parameter models evaluation metrics (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Effect	Metric	Mean Error against Target Audio			
		Input Audio	Output Audio	Δ	$\Delta\%$
<i>Compressor</i>	MSE	2.21	0.80	-1.41	-63.62
	MAE	11.35	5.91	-5.45	-47.98
	LSD	10.65	5.92	-4.73	-44.43
	MFCCD	115.04	60.84	-54.20	-47.11
	PCC	82.37	91.12	8.75	10.62
	MSSMAE	67.50	37.69	-29.81	-44.16
<i>Distortion</i>	MSE	5.09	1.15	-3.94	-77.41
	MAE	14.23	6.78	-7.45	-52.37
	LSD	13.74	7.17	-6.57	-47.83
	MFCCD	139.29	67.49	-71.80	-51.54
	PCC	71.37	84.34	12.97	18.17
	MSSMAE	69.34	48.78	-20.56	-29.65
<i>Equalizer</i>	MSE	1.50	0.71	-0.79	-52.74
	MAE	8.35	5.33	-3.02	-36.18
	LSD	8.27	5.52	-2.76	-33.30
	MFCCD	88.96	56.25	-32.71	-36.77
	PCC	88.38	91.69	3.31	3.75
	MSSMAE	62.99	46.15	-16.84	-26.74
<i>Phaser</i> ¹	MSE	0.80	0.70	-0.09	-11.69
	MAE	6.55	5.63	-0.91	-13.94
	LSD	6.68	5.89	-0.79	-11.84
	MFCCD	68.99	59.44	-9.55	-13.84
	PCC	89.92	89.20	-0.72	-0.80
	MSSMAE	43.06	33.07	-9.99	-23.21
<i>Hall Reverb</i>	MSE	1.21	0.33	-0.88	-72.56
	MAE	8.34	3.72	-4.62	-55.39
	LSD	7.98	3.97	-4.02	-50.31
	MFCCD	73.80	36.81	-36.99	-50.12
	PCC	84.07	93.57	9.50	11.30
	MSSMAE	52.58	24.58	-28.00	-53.25

¹Phaser specific details are provided in Section 4.4.2.

Table B.2: Evaluation metrics for the *Oracle* baseline (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.24	1.24	-4.00	-76.39	-1.28	-1.43	-1.30	-1.41	-1.15
MAE	16.83	7.34	-9.49	-56.38	-3.45	-3.36	-2.83	-2.93	-2.41
LSD	15.69	7.49	-8.19	-52.22	-3.00	-2.81	-2.52	-2.51	-2.13
MFCCD	166.78	74.66	-92.12	-55.23	-33.20	-31.97	-28.65	-28.42	-23.87
PCC	66.01	84.79	18.78	28.45	6.76	5.81	6.25	6.10	5.92
MSSMAE	87.41	46.25	-41.16	-47.09	-18.13	-12.40	-12.67	-10.18	-7.17

Table B.3: Evaluation metrics for *SerumRNN* (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.25	1.16	-4.08	-77.83	-2.58	-0.93	-0.39	-0.21	-0.08
MAE	16.82	7.20	-9.62	-57.19	-5.80	-2.23	-1.05	-0.66	-0.16
LSD	15.69	7.34	-8.35	-53.25	-5.09	-1.86	-0.92	-0.57	-0.18
MFCCD	166.76	72.68	-94.08	-56.42	-55.78	-22.05	-10.78	-6.57	-2.03
PCC	65.97	86.00	20.03	30.37	13.02	3.33	2.06	1.76	1.19
MSSMAE	87.18	44.85	-42.32	-48.55	-21.67	-13.33	-3.46	-3.36	-1.95

Table B.4: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumRNN NI* baseline (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.26	1.47	-3.79	-72.05	-1.30	-1.84	-0.53	-0.18	-0.08
MAE	16.86	7.84	-9.02	-53.48	-3.49	-3.60	-1.54	-0.59	-0.28
LSD	15.71	7.96	-7.75	-49.31	-3.03	-3.09	-1.30	-0.50	-0.22
MFCCD	166.92	80.57	-86.36	-51.73	-32.56	-35.36	-14.79	-5.49	-3.01
PCC	65.85	85.08	19.23	29.21	5.52	8.11	4.66	1.55	0.70
MSSMAE	87.26	46.59	-40.67	-46.60	-23.23	-8.75	-5.07	-2.37	-3.39

Table B.5: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN* baseline (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.25	1.80	-3.45	-65.72	-1.11	-1.45	-0.75	-0.27	-0.06
MAE	16.83	8.33	-8.50	-50.53	-3.16	-2.97	-1.88	-0.85	-0.26
LSD	15.69	8.44	-7.25	-46.21	-2.76	-2.51	-1.63	-0.65	-0.17
MFCCD	166.83	85.82	-81.01	-48.56	-29.53	-29.51	-17.82	-7.63	-2.24
PCC	65.88	85.20	19.32	29.33	4.21	7.54	5.91	2.52	0.80
MSSMAE	87.27	45.32	-41.95	-48.07	-23.64	-6.67	-7.22	-4.37	-1.88

 Table B.6: Evaluation metrics for the *Random* baseline (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.26	2.12	-3.14	-59.75	-0.82	-1.00	-0.86	-0.64	-0.39
MAE	16.85	9.65	-7.20	-42.74	-1.87	-2.16	-1.97	-1.49	-1.15
LSD	15.72	9.51	-6.21	-39.51	-1.59	-1.81	-1.69	-1.45	-0.89
MFCCD	167.09	97.39	-69.70	-41.72	-18.00	-20.36	-19.28	-15.82	-10.06
PCC	65.89	81.03	15.14	22.98	3.53	4.85	3.87	4.28	3.00
MSSMAE	87.22	51.92	-35.30	-40.47	-9.61	-8.92	-8.06	-8.46	-4.78

 Table B.7: Evaluation metrics for the *SerumCNN 1S* baseline (*Basic Shapes* preset group).

Metric	Mean Error against Target				Mean Error Δ per Step				
	Init.	Final	Δ	$\Delta\%$	1	2	3	4	5
MSE	5.25	1.69	-3.56	-67.85	-1.04	-1.67	-0.78	-0.18	-0.06
MAE	16.83	8.31	-8.52	-50.61	-3.02	-3.29	-1.94	-0.57	-0.22
LSD	15.69	8.33	-7.36	-46.90	-2.60	-2.83	-1.70	-0.46	-0.21
MFCCD	166.84	84.24	-82.60	-49.51	-27.78	-33.22	-18.59	-5.66	-2.82
PCC	65.95	84.88	18.93	28.70	3.61	8.53	5.58	2.09	0.45
MSSMAE	87.19	47.13	-40.06	-45.95	-23.96	-6.16	-7.53	-1.35	-2.79

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Acronyms

AI artificial intelligence.

BPM beats per minute.

CNN convolutional neural network.

DAW digital audio workstation.

DL deep learning.

FFT fast Fourier transform.

LFO low frequency oscillator.

LSTM long short-term memory.

MFCC Mel frequency cepstral coefficients.

MIDI musical instrument digital interface.

RNN recurrent neural network.

STFT short-time Fourier transform.

UI user interface.

UX user experience.

VAE variational autoencoder.

VST Virtual Studio Technology.

Bibliography

- [1] Steve Duda. *Serum: Advanced Wavetable Synthesizer*. 2014. URL: <https://xferrecords.com/products/serum>.
- [2] Ian Simon et al. *Learning a Latent Space of Multitrack Measures*. 2018. arXiv: 1806.00195 [stat.ML].
- [3] David Ha and Douglas Eck. “A Neural Representation of Sketch Drawings”. In: *ICLR 2018*. 2018. 2018. URL: <https://openreview.net/pdf?id=Hy6GHpkCW>.
- [4] David Moffat and Mark B. Sandler. “Approaches in Intelligent Music Production”. In: *Arts* 8.4 (2019). ISSN: 2076-0752. DOI: 10.3390/arts8040125. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-0752/8/4/125>.
- [5] Leon Fedden. *RenderMan: Command Line VSTi Audio, Features and Parameter Renderer*. 2018. URL: <https://github.com/fedden/RenderMan>.
- [6] Brian McFee et al. “librosa: Audio and music signal analysis in python.” In: *Python in Science Conference*. 2015.
- [7] Colin Raffel and Daniel P. W. Ellis. “Intuitive Analysis, Creation and Manipulation of MIDI Data with pretty_midi”. In: *ISMIR*. 2014.
- [8] Google Magenta. *Magenta NoteSequence*. 2016. URL: <https://github.com/magenta/note-seq>.
- [9] Nathan Sommer and A. Ralescu. “Developing a Machine Learning Approach to Controlling Musical Synthesizer Parameters in Real-Time Live Performance”. In: *MAICS*. 2014.
- [10] Bo-Yu Chen, Jordan B. L. Smith, and Yi-Hsuan Yang. *Neural Loop Combiner: Neural Network Models for Assessing the Compatibility of Loops*. 2020. arXiv: 2008.02011 [cs.SD].
- [11] Vibert Thio and Chris Donahue. “Neural Loops”. In: *NeurIPS Workshop on Machine Learning for Creativity and Design*. 2019.
- [12] Romain Hennequin et al. “Spleeter: a fast and efficient music source separation tool with pre-trained models”. In: *Journal of Open Source Software* 5.50 (2020). Deezee Research, p. 2154. DOI: 10.21105/joss.02154. URL: <https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.02154>.
- [13] Adam Roberts et al. “Magenta Studio: Augmenting Creativity with Deep Learning in Ableton Live”. In: *Proceedings of the International Workshop on Musical Metacreation (MUME)*.
- [14] Aaron van den Oord et al. *WaveNet: A Generative Model for Raw Audio*. 2016. arXiv: 1609.03499 [cs.SD].
- [15] Soroush Mehri et al. *SampleRNN: An Unconditional End-to-End Neural Audio Generation Model*. 2017. arXiv: 1612.07837 [cs.SD].

- [16] Nal Kalchbrenner et al. *Efficient Neural Audio Synthesis*. 2018. arXiv: 1802.08435 [cs.SD].
- [17] Prateek Verma and C. Chafe. “A Generative Model for Raw Audio Using Transformer Architectures”. In: 2021.
- [18] Prafulla Dhariwal et al. *Jukebox: A Generative Model for Music*. 2020. arXiv: 2005.00341 [eess.AS].
- [19] Alexandre Défossez et al. “SING: Symbol-to-Instrument Neural Generator”. In: *NeurIPS*. 2018.
- [20] Sercan Ö. Arik, Heewoo Jun, and G. Diamos. “Fast Spectrogram Inversion Using Multi-Head Convolutional Neural Networks”. In: *IEEE Signal Processing Letters* 26 (2019), pp. 94–98.
- [21] Chris Donahue, Julian McAuley, and Miller Puckette. *Adversarial Audio Synthesis*. 2019. arXiv: 1802.04208 [cs.SD].
- [22] Yuxuan Wang et al. “Tacotron: Towards End-to-End Speech Synthesis”. In: *INTER-SPEECH*. 2017.
- [23] Jesse Engel et al. *GANSynth: Adversarial Neural Audio Synthesis*. 2019. arXiv: 1902.08710 [cs.SD].
- [24] Jesse Engel et al. *Neural Audio Synthesis of Musical Notes with WaveNet Autoencoders*. 2017. arXiv: 1704.01279 [cs.LG].
- [25] Jesse Engel et al. “DDSP: Differentiable Digital Signal Processing”. In: *International Conference on Learning Representations*. 2020. URL: <https://openreview.net/forum?id=B1x1ma4tDr>.
- [26] M. A. M. Ramírez and J. Reiss. “End-to-end equalization with convolutional neural networks”. In: *Proceedings of the 21st International Conference on Digital Audio Effects (DAFx-18)*. 2018.
- [27] M. M. Ramírez, Emmanouil Benetos, and J. Reiss. “Modeling Plate and Spring Reverberation Using A DSP-Informed Deep Neural Network”. In: *ICASSP 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (2020), pp. 241–245.
- [28] M. M. Ramírez and J. Reiss. “Modeling Nonlinear Audio Effects with End-to-end Deep Neural Networks”. In: *ICASSP 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (2019), pp. 171–175.
- [29] Marco A. Martínez Ramírez, Emmanouil Benetos, and Joshua D. Reiss. “Deep Learning for Black-Box Modeling of Audio Effects”. In: *Applied Sciences* 10.2 (2020). ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app10020638. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/2/638>.
- [30] Shahan Nercessian, Andy Sarroff, and Kurt James Werner. *Lightweight and interpretable neural modeling of an audio distortion effect using hyperconditioned differentiable biquads*. 2021. arXiv: 2103.08709 [eess.AS].
- [31] Eero-Pekka Damskägg et al. “Deep Learning for Tube Amplifier Emulation”. In: *ICASSP 2019 - 2019 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (2019), pp. 471–475.
- [32] Alec Wright et al. “Real-Time Guitar Amplifier Emulation with Deep Learning”. In: *Applied Sciences* 10 (2020), p. 766.
- [33] Christian J. Steinmetz and Joshua D. Reiss. *Efficient Neural Networks for Real-time Analog Audio Effect Modeling*. 2021. arXiv: 2102.06200 [eess.AS].

- [34] E. Ly and Julián Villegas. “Genetic Reverb: Synthesizing Artificial Reverberant Fields via Genetic Algorithms”. In: *EvoMUSART*. 2020.
- [35] Sebastian Heise, Michael Hlatky, and Jörn Loviscach. “Automatic Cloning of Recorded Sounds by Software Synthesizers”. In: *Journal of The Audio Engineering Society* (2009).
- [36] Juan-Pablo Cáceres. *Sound Design Learning for Frequency Modulation Synthesis Parameters*. 2007.
- [37] Matthieu Macret and Philippe Pasquier. “Automatic Design of Sound Synthesizers as Pure Data Patches Using Coevolutionary Mixed-Typed Cartesian Genetic Programming”. In: *Proceedings of the 2014 Annual Conference on Genetic and Evolutionary Computation*. GECCO ’14. Vancouver, BC, Canada, 2014, pp. 309–316. ISBN: 9781450326629. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/2576768.2598303>.
- [38] K. Tatar, Matthieu Macret, and P. Pasquier. “Automatic Synthesizer Preset Generation with PresetGen”. In: *Journal of New Music Research* 45 (2016), pp. 124–144.
- [39] Benjamin D. Smith. “Play it Again: Evolved Audio Effects and Synthesizer Programming”. In: *Computational Intelligence in Music, Sound, Art and Design*. Ed. by João Correia, Vic Ciesielski, and Antonios Liapis. Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2017, pp. 275–288.
- [40] M. J. Yee-King, L. Fedden, and M. d’Inverno. “Automatic Programming of VST Sound Synthesizers Using Deep Networks and Other Techniques”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Emerging Topics in Computational Intelligence* 2.2 (2018), pp. 150–159. DOI: 10.1109/TETCI.2017.2783885.
- [41] O. Barkan et al. “InverSynth: Deep Estimation of Synthesizer Parameter Configurations From Audio Signals”. In: *IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing* 27.12 (2019), pp. 2385–2396. DOI: 10.1109/TASLP.2019.2944568.
- [42] Philippe Esling et al. “Flow Synthesizer: Universal Audio Synthesizer Control with Normalizing Flows”. In: *Applied Sciences* 10.1 (2020). ISSN: 2076-3417. DOI: 10.3390/app10010302. URL: <https://www.mdpi.com/2076-3417/10/1/302>.
- [43] S. Mimilakis, Nicholas J. Bryan, and P. Smaragdis. “One-Shot Parametric Audio Production Style Transfer with Application to Frequency Equalization”. In: *ICASSP 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (2020), pp. 256–260.
- [44] Di Sheng and Gyorgy Fazekas. “A Feature Learning Siamese Model for Intelligent Control of the Dynamic Range Compressor”. In: *2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)* (2019), pp. 1–8.
- [45] Christian J. Steinmetz et al. “Automatic multitrack mixing with a differentiable mixing console of neural audio effects”. In: *ICASSP*. 2021.
- [46] Marco A. Martínez Ramírez et al. *Differentiable Signal Processing With Black-Box Audio Effects*. 2021. arXiv: 2105.04752 [eess.AS].
- [47] Yuanming Hu et al. “Exposure: A White-Box Photo Post-Processing Framework”. In: *ACM Trans. Graph.* 37.2 (May 2018). ISSN: 0730-0301. DOI: 10.1145/3181974. URL: <https://doi.org/10.1145/3181974>.
- [48] Shulei Ji, Jing Luo, and Xinyu Yang. *A Comprehensive Survey on Deep Music Generation: Multi-level Representations, Algorithms, Evaluations, and Future Directions*. 2020. arXiv: 2011.06801 [cs.SD].

- [49] Adam Roberts et al. *A Hierarchical Latent Vector Model for Learning Long-Term Structure in Music*. 2019. arXiv: 1803.05428 [cs.LG].
- [50] Ziyu Wang et al. *PIANOTREE VAE: Structured Representation Learning for Polyphonic Music*. 2020. arXiv: 2008.07118 [eess.AS].
- [51] Yichao Zhou et al. “BandNet: A Neural Network-based, Multi-Instrument Beatles-Style MIDI Music Composition Machine”. In: *ISMIR*. 2019.
- [52] Hao-Wen Dong et al. “MuseGAN: Multi-track Sequential Generative Adversarial Networks for Symbolic Music Generation and Accompaniment”. In: *AAAI*. 2018.
- [53] Faqian Guan, Chunyan Yu, and Suqiong Yang. “A GAN Model With Self-attention Mechanism To Generate Multi-instruments Symbolic Music”. In: *2019 International Joint Conference on Neural Networks (IJCNN)* (2019), pp. 1–6.
- [54] Cheng-Zhi Anna Huang et al. “Music Transformer: Generating Music with Long-Term Structure”. In: *ICLR*. 2019.
- [55] Yu-Siang Huang and Yi-Hsuan Yang. *Pop Music Transformer: Beat-based Modeling and Generation of Expressive Pop Piano Compositions*. 2020. arXiv: 2002.00212 [cs.SD].
- [56] Junyan Jiang et al. “Transformer VAE: A Hierarchical Model for Structure-Aware and Interpretable Music Representation Learning”. In: *ICASSP 2020 - 2020 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP)* (2020), pp. 516–520.
- [57] Shih-Lun Wu and Yi-Hsuan Yang. *MuseMorphose: Full-Song and Fine-Grained Music Style Transfer with Just One Transformer VAE*. 2021. arXiv: 2105.04090 [cs.SD].
- [58] Jon Gillick et al. *Learning to Groove with Inverse Sequence Transformations*. 2019. arXiv: 1905.06118 [cs.SD].
- [59] Ian Simon and Sageev Oore. *Performance RNN: Generating Music with Expressive Timing and Dynamics*. Blog. 2017. URL: <https://magenta.tensorflow.org/performance-rnn>.
- [60] Dorien Herremans and E. Chew. “MorpheuS: Generating Structured Music with Constrained Patterns and Tension”. In: *IEEE Transactions on Affective Computing* 10 (2019), pp. 510–523.
- [61] Rui Guo et al. *A variational autoencoder for music generation controlled by tonal tension*. 2020. arXiv: 2010.06230 [cs.SD].
- [62] Andrea Valenti, Antonio Carta, and D. Bacciu. “Learning Style-Aware Symbolic Music Representations by Adversarial Autoencoders”. In: *ECAI*. 2020.
- [63] Gautam Mittal et al. *Symbolic Music Generation with Diffusion Models*. 2021. arXiv: 2103.16091 [cs.SD].
- [64] Yijun Zhou et al. *Generative Melody Composition with Human-in-the-Loop Bayesian Optimization*. 2020. arXiv: 2010.03190 [cs.SD].
- [65] Vibert Thio and Douglas Eck. *Lo-Fi Player*. Blog. 2020. URL: <https://magenta.tensorflow.org/lofi-player>.
- [66] Nitish Srivastava et al. “Dropout: a simple way to prevent neural networks from overfitting”. In: *J. Mach. Learn. Res.* 15 (2014), pp. 1929–1958.
- [67] Djork-Arné Clevert, Thomas Unterthiner, and Sepp Hochreiter. *Fast and Accurate Deep Network Learning by Exponential Linear Units (ELUs)*. 2016. arXiv: 1511.07289 [cs.LG].

-
- [68] Diederik P. Kingma and Jimmy Ba. *Adam: A Method for Stochastic Optimization*. 2017. arXiv: 1412.6980 [cs.LG].
- [69] Collin Raffel. *Learning-Based Methods for Comparing Sequences, with Applications to Audio-to-Midi Alignment and Matching*. PhD Thesis. 2016. URL: <https://colinraffel.com/publications/thesis.pdf>.
- [70] Leland McInnes, John Healy, and James Melville. *UMAP: Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection for Dimension Reduction*. 2020. arXiv: 1802.03426 [stat.ML].
- [71] Nicholas Carlini et al. *Extracting Training Data from Large Language Models*. 2021. arXiv: 2012.07805 [cs.CR].